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1. Changes with respect to the description of work

No changes to deliverable scope.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable is public and will be available at ELEVATE's website.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This report brings together four studies that address critical questions at the intersection of solar geoengineering, carbon dioxide removal (CDR), and climate policy. The first study examines public perceptions of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) in Mexico, the United States, and the United Kingdom using nationally representative surveys. Results show that support is highest in Mexico, while information framing has only limited effects. Universities are viewed as more legitimate actors than start-ups, though overall perceptions of risks and benefits remain similar across countries.

The second study focuses on CDR, using surveys of 800 participants each in five countries (Brazil, Kenya, Germany, the United States, and China). Support varies strongly across countries, with Brazil and Kenya most supportive and Germany least supportive of direct air capture (DAC) and enhanced rock weathering (ERW). Across all countries, afforestation and reforestation attract the strongest support, while DAC is consistently the least favoured. Policies emphasizing nature protection and mitigation are better received than those involving taxation.

The third study develops a novel modelling framework combining an Earth system emulator with a country-level integrated assessment model to analyse regional heterogeneity in SAI impacts. Cooperative global governance delivers welfare improvements, while unilateral deployment by major emitters risks asymmetric strategies with harmful side effects on equatorial and tropical regions, highlighting the governance risks of uncoordinated action.

Finally, the fourth study explores intertemporal financing mechanisms for negative emissions. Using a stylized integrated assessment model, it shows how different pricing rules affect mitigation pathways, wealth transfers across generations, and ethical considerations surrounding market-based incentives for CDR.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

We have consolidated our work and findings into four major studies, which are detailed in the report below:

1. Like diamonds in the sky? Public perceptions, governance, and information framing of solar geoengineering activities in Mexico, the United Kingdom, and the United States
2. Understanding Public Support for CDR: Insights from Five Countries
3. Regional implications of noncooperative stratospheric aerosol injection
4. Intertemporal funding of negative emissions in a multi-regional integrated assessment model

These studies address the objectives of Deliverable 4.2 and Task 4.2, as outlined in the table below.

Goals	Studies	1	2	3	4
Review the governance literature about climate Interventions		Introduces and reviews SAI options	Introduces and reviews CDR options	Introduces and reviews SAI options	Introduces and reviews CDR options
Original survey and experimental work to test how climate interventions interact with climate mitigation and which provisions are needed to minimize crowding out of ambition		Carried out survey work on public perceptions focusing on geoengineering options	Carried out experimental work on public support for CDR options, both Natural and technological		
For SRM, the task will review the political economy literature and		By surveying public		Models the governance of SRM	

<p>discuss the risks of unilateral deployment and the international repercussions that regional or global interventions might have</p>	<p>perceptions on SAI, it contributes to the debate on SAI governance</p>		<p>interventions using cooperative and non-cooperative scenarios using an IAM and ML aerosol emulator for differentiated altitude injections.</p>	
<p>For CO₂ removals, this task will discuss ways to make emitters accountable via Carbon Removal Obligations</p>				<p>Models and discusses funding needs for CDR using a global IAM</p>

Version log

Version	Date	Released by	Nature of Change
1	23-09-2025	Chad Baum and Lara Aleluia	First draft, for internal review
2	01-10-2025	Chad Baum and Lara Aleluia	Second version, after internal review
3	08-10-2025	Chad Baum and Lara Aleluia	Final version, for submission

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1. Like diamonds in the sky? Public perceptions, governance, and information framing of solar geoengineering activities in Mexico, the United Kingdom, and the United States

This study has already been published and it is available at <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09644016.2023.2301262> where the full detailed study can be found. We hereafter provide the abstract.

Abstract

Solar geoengineering (also known as solar radiation modification) is garnering more attention (and controversy) among media and policymakers in response to the impacts of climate change. Such debates have become more prominent following the first-ever field trials of stratospheric aerosol injection (SAI) in 2022. How the lay public perceives solar geoengineering remains unclear, however. We use nationally representative samples (N = 3013) in Mexico, United States, and United Kingdom to examine public perceptions of risks and benefits, support, and policy preferences. We also employ an information-framing design that presents individuals with media-style reports on SAI activities differing along three dimensions: location, actor, and scale and purpose. Support for SAI is found to be generally higher in Mexico; perceptions of risks and benefits do not differ between countries. Information about SAI activities has a limited effect. There is evidence that activities conducted by universities receive more support than those by start-up companies.

2. Understanding Public Support for CDR: Insights from Five Countries

Abstract

The set of five nationally representative surveys (N=800 participants in each country) identified significant differences in the level of support of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies across countries, notably with higher support on average in Brazil and Kenya, whereas Germany was the least supportive of direct air capture (DAC) and enhanced rock weathering (ERW). Those in the United States and China were typically in the middle. We also identified a clear preference among the CDR options, where support of afforestation and reforestation was significantly higher than DAC or ERW - irrespective of country or location of activity. Additionally, ERW often received more support than DAC, most consistently in Germany and the United States. This was also true for Brazil and Kenya whenever ERW vis-a-vis DAC was to be done in one's own

community. Differences in support could also be identified depending on the location of the activity for all countries except Germany. Notably, activities broadly in the country rather than in one's community received higher support for DAC or ERW – and less so, but in some cases for afforestation and reforestation in Brazil and China. Regarding support for environmental policies, the most-supported policies related to “nature protection”, followed by “mitigation” investments. Policies involving taxes received by far the least support. Given that CDR investments received a middling level of support, we can conclude that this is far from the most-preferred policy option but could nonetheless be a worthwhile part of the broader policy portfolio.

Introduction

Developing and implementing carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies at the scale required requires that the public be engaged and involved at an early stage and in an ongoing fashion. As a result, it is important to better understand the rationales and motivations of public support, that is to investigate the determinants of public perceptions, including how these differ between technologies and across countries at a global level. One way to identify key determinants of support of CDR technologies is to investigate why some people are supportive while others are not: in other words, to analyse inter-individual differences. Economics and other social sciences assume that individual differences in people's tendencies to take risks, delay outcomes, and act pro-socially (often referred to as economic preferences) can explain why people behave differently. The present report therefore draws upon a novel dataset gathered in August and September of 2025 which explores whether six individual preference measures (risk taking, patience, altruism, positive reciprocity, negative reciprocity, and trust) predict the support for three different carbon dioxide removal technologies: direct air capture, enhanced rock weathering, and afforestation and reforestation. This is based on primary data from nationally representative samples (N=800) in five countries (US, Germany, Brazil, China, Kenya), with the survey conducted in five languages (English in the United States; German in Germany; Portuguese in Brazil; simplified Mandarin in China; Swahili and English in Kenya).

Methods

Survey data collection and procedures

The preliminary findings reported here are based on primary data from nationally representative samples (N=800) from five countries (US, Germany, Brazil, China, Kenya), with the survey conducted in five languages (English in the United States; German in Germany; Portuguese in Brazil; simplified Mandarin in China; Swahili and English in Kenya). Surveys were nationally representative in terms of age, gender, income, education, geographic region, and geographic area, i.e. urban versus rural.

The main purpose of the survey was to examine perceptions and support of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies and climate policies across 5 countries (United States, Brazil, Kenya, Germany, and China), along with identifying key determinants that related to support and perceptions. We specifically examined public perceptions of three carbon dioxide removal technologies (Direct Air Capture, Afforestation and Reforestation, and Enhanced Rock Weathering) to identify potential divergence in how these are perceived. In this vein, we also employed different measures for support, related to the perceived role of the technology in helping to deal with climate change, one's own level of support if the technology would be developed and deployed either in one's country or within one's own community, respectively, how much participants would expect other members of their community to support the technology being developed and deployed, again, in their country or within their community. The latter two questions were first and foremost used as a check of social desirability bias.

To gain insights into their underlying rationale, participants were also asked to select which reasons from a list of ten possibilities most informed their support decisions. This question not only helped provide greater context into their decisions but also allowed us to investigate the relative prominence of certain rationales across both technologies and countries.

The second set of dependent variables related to a question block about the level of support or opposition for twelve different types of climate policies. These included: policies that made use of taxes (e.g. on gas and fossil fuels, carbon emissions of airplane companies, or foods high in carbon emissions such as meat and dairy), subsidies and investments (e.g. in renewable energy sources, in green jobs and businesses, or infrastructure for bicycling and transportation), promoted natural protections (e.g. on forested and natural grassland areas, or keeping waterways and oceans clean), and some behavioural nudge-style approaches (i.e. making green energy the default in energy contracts, or informing households of how their energy consumption compared to their neighbours). By including "investing more in technologies that remove carbon dioxide removal from the air", we could also consider the relative preference here vis-à-vis other policy options.

Regarding potential determinants, we asked participants about their prior familiarity with each of the carbon dioxide removal technologies, a variety of climate beliefs and motivations, their level of trust in five types of actors and institutions (e.g. universities, NGOs, national governments), their aversion to tampering with nature, and how much they perceived science and technology as a solution to climate change.

As part of an additional set of hypotheses, we measure several additional variables to better understanding potential associations between economic preferences and support for the carbon dioxide removal strategies. In specific, we measured each participant's preferences across six domains (risk taking, patience, positive reciprocity,

negative reciprocity, altruism, and trust) using validated survey questions adapted from ¹. Results related to these measures are not the focus of the current report.

Randomization and Quality control

Participants were recruited through a professional survey company. This company facilitated the translation of the survey into the relevant languages (German in Germany, simplified Chinese for China, Portuguese in Brazil, and Swahili in Kenya) and paid participants according to their established rates, as well as facilitated the programming and scripting of layouts for both handheld and desktop devices. There were attention checks during the survey, and a comprehension check following each of the information texts. If participants failed one of the comprehension checks three times (while giving them the opportunity to re-read the text after an incorrect answer), they will be excluded from the study - we opted for this approach to not exclude those who might not have initially understood details about the technologies given their potential unfamiliarity and/or complexity. Exclusion will also occur if participants miss any of the attention checks. The survey firm will also impose speeder checks (less than 30% of the median completion time for the survey) and apply quality checks, e.g. for duplicate or artificial IP addresses. Participants must be at least 18 years old.

Participants were also randomly assigned into two blocks: one where they will answer questions about economic preferences followed by the information on climate change and the CDR technologies, and the other in the opposite order. The order in which information about the three CDR technologies (i.e. direct air capture, enhanced rock weathering, and afforestation and reforestation) and the environmental policies was also randomized across participants. We randomize the blocks of participants to avoid ordering effects, specifically in relation to how the CDR technologies are presented. The variation in where economic preferences appear in the survey is done to assess (and control for) any bias related to how the context of climate change might affect responses to economic preferences. Questions within blocks with multiple items were also randomized.

Results

Familiarity and Levels of Support for Three Carbon Dioxide Removal Technologies

First, we present the descriptive statistics related to familiarity and the mean levels of support for the three technologies across the five countries. We also consider the extent to which support for carbon removal technologies depended on whether these are to be developed and deployed "in their country" rather than "in their community" (as an illustration of potential NIMBYism). We also compare means for the different carbon dioxide removal technologies to see if they differed in terms of support.

Familiarity

The first result to underscore is that familiarity is quite low across participants and across all countries regarding direct air capture and enhanced rock weathering (see Table 1). Indeed, participants in the United States expressed only slight familiarity even with afforestation and reforestation.

Table 1: Familiarity across countries (1-5 scale, 1= not at all familiar; 5=very familiar)

		Familiarity with technologies		
Country		Direct Air Capture	Afforestation and Reforestation	Enhanced Rock Weathering
Germany	Mean	1.80	3.83	1.48
	N	809	809	809
	Std. Deviation	1.138	1.187	.873
China	Mean	2.94	4.12	2.86
	N	801	801	801
	Std. Deviation	1.356	1.004	1.407
Brazil	Mean	2.18	3.92	1.98
	N	801	801	801
	Std. Deviation	1.314	1.280	1.244
Kenya	Mean	2.17	4.77	2.17
	N	804	804	804
	Std. Deviation	1.331	.682	1.324
USA	Mean	2.32	3.19	2.23
	N	800	800	800
	Std. Deviation	1.470	1.575	1.433
Total	Mean	2.28	3.97	2.14
	N	4015	4015	4015
	Std. Deviation	1.376	1.287	1.346

The fact that familiarity remains generally low also presents some difficulties for the more detailed regression analyses. For instance, participants' perceptions of the technologies could equally reflect broader anxieties about unfamiliar technologies, or even climate change in general, rather than well-formed views. On the one hand, this is a recurring challenge when doing research into public attitudes with emerging technologies – and always deserves to be highlighted. On the other hand, real-world views and perceptions of lay individuals are also informed by such considerations. As such, it is not the case that this is an inherent limitation of survey-based research, let alone one that necessarily impedes its external validity. In sum, the fact that publics around the world are unfamiliar with these technologies represents a key challenge.

In any case, our future analysis, notably, regressions examining the factor that affects support or opposition of CDR will include familiarity as a control variable; we will also explore if the relevance of this factor differs at a country level.

Support – Direct Air Capture

We also identified significant differences in level of support for the carbon dioxide removal technologies across all countries. Starting with direct air capture, we find that – according to independent-samples Kruskal-Wallis H testing, $H(4)=629.573$, $p>.001$ – this technology was seen to play a bigger role in addressing climate change in Brazil ($M=76.97$) and Kenya ($M=73.50$), followed by China ($M=70.02$) and the United States ($M=64.48$). In contrast, direct air capture was viewed much less positively in Germany ($M=43.20$). The pattern of answers was similar for the questions about the level of support, whether in one’s own community or the country at large (see Table 2).

We did however identify significant differences in the level of support of direct air capture, depending on the location of the activity. According to paired-samples t -testing, support was higher in all countries if direct air capture were being developed and deployed in the country rather than within one’s own community: in the United States, mean difference= 2.066 , $t(767)= 4.465$, $p<.001$; in Kenya, mean difference= 1.706 , $t(799)= 3.373$, $p<.001$; in Brazil, mean difference= 1.990 , $t(776)= 4.692$, $p<.001$; in China, mean difference= 1.703 , $t(780)= 3.668$, $p<.001$; and Germany, mean difference= 2.467 , $t(744)= 6.625$, $p<.001$.

Table 2: Support for Direct air capture across countries (0-100 scale, 0= no role at all, 100=a major role; 0=strongly oppose, 100=strongly support)

		Support for Direct Air Capture		
Country		DAC Role Addressing Climate Change	DAC Support in Country	DAC Support in Community
Germany	Mean	43.20	44.22	41.54
	N	741	761	750
	Std. Deviation	28.568	28.720	29.915
China	Mean	70.04	68.79	67.12
	N	780	787	782
	Std. Deviation	22.135	23.395	25.978
Brazil	Mean	76.97	71.52	69.67
	N	780	787	778
	Std. Deviation	25.538	29.800	30.277
Kenya	Mean	73.50	73.06	71.35
	N	788	802	801
	Std. Deviation	26.530	29.122	30.579
USA	Mean	64.48	64.96	62.67
	N	761	777	777
	Std. Deviation	29.126	29.563	30.416
Total	Mean	65.89	64.68	62.68
	N	3850	3914	3888
	Std. Deviation	28.969	30.068	31.367

Support – Afforestation and Reforestation

Turning to afforestation and reforestation, we again find that the level of support significantly differed across all countries (see Table 3). According to independent-samples Kruskal-Wallis H testing, $H(4)=585.237, p>.001$, afforestation was envisioned to play a bigger role in addressing climate change in Brazil ($M=92.04$) and Kenya ($M=92.06$). No significant differences between China ($M=82.27$), Germany ($M=81.50$), and USA ($M=79.29$) could be identified, though these were generally lower than in the other countries.

Moreover, if we look at the questions related to support, we can identify some more significant differences between the countries. Participants were most supportive of developing and deploying afforestation and reforestation in Kenya ($M=95.32$ in country; $M=95.10$ within their own community), followed by Brazil ($M=92.18$; $M=91.35$), then Germany ($M=86.31$; $M=86.28$). Conversely, people were relatively less supportive of afforestation and reforestation in China ($M=83.88$; $M=83.05$) and the United States ($M=81.70$; $M=81.23$). In any case, the level of support of afforestation

and reforestation was still significantly higher than for direct air capture across all countries (according to paired-samples t-testing).

In contrast to the other carbon removal technologies, the location of the activity had a more limited role for afforestation and reforestation. Notably, whether the activity was being done broadly in the country or within one’s own community had no significant impact, according to paired-samples t-testing, in the United States ($p=0.366$), Kenya ($p=0.406$), and Germany ($p=0.799$). There was a significant but small in magnitude difference for both Brazil – mean difference=0.834, $t(798)= 2.331$, $p=.020$ – and China – mean difference=0.812, $t(797)=2.072$, $p=.039$. In both countries, participants were slightly less supportive if afforestation and reforestation were to happen within their own communities.

Table 3: Support for Afforestation and reforestation across countries (0-100 scale, 0=no role at all, 100=a major role; 0=strongly oppose, 100=strongly support)

Country		Support for Afforestation		
		Afforestation Role Addressing Climate Change	Afforestation Support in Country	Afforestation Support in Community
Germany	Mean	81.50	86.31	86.28
	N	788	792	787
	Std. Deviation	17.608	16.352	16.756
China	Mean	82.28	83.90	83.07
	N	797	799	798
	Std. Deviation	12.952	14.072	14.974
Brazil	Mean	92.04	92.18	91.35
	N	795	800	799
	Std. Deviation	11.961	13.979	15.828
Kenya	Mean	92.06	95.32	95.10
	N	803	804	804
	Std. Deviation	12.649	10.137	10.895
USA	Mean	79.29	81.70	81.23
	N	778	780	777
	Std. Deviation	19.457	19.593	19.597
Total	Mean	85.48	87.93	87.45
	N	3961	3975	3965
	Std. Deviation	16.151	15.950	16.646

Support – Enhanced Rock Weathering

Finally, regarding enhanced rock weathering, this also significantly differed across all countries. According to independent-samples Kruskal-Wallis H testing, $H(4)=520.275$, $p>.001$, Enhanced Rock Weathering was envisioned to play a more important role in

addressing climate change in Brazil (M=76.71), followed by Kenya (M=72.76), and then China (M=69.77) and the USA (M=65.96) – the latter two did not significantly differ. However, the lowest level of support by far was found for enhanced rock weathering in Germany (M=47.65).

According to paired-samples T-tests, there were significant differences according to the location of the activity, depending on the country: in China, mean difference=1.480 $t(780)= 3.551, p<.001$; in Brazil, mean difference=1.051, $t(768)=2.951, p=.003$; in Kenya, mean difference=1.060, $t(799)= 2.571, p=.014$; and in the United States, mean difference=2.544, $t(757)= 6.176, p<.001$. No significant differences could be found in Germany, $t(730)=1.666, p=.096$. For four of the five countries, there was thus greater support for enhanced rock weathering being done not within one’s own community.

Table 4: Support for Enhanced rock weathering across countries (0-100 scale, 0= no role at all, 100=a major role; 0=strongly oppose, 100=strongly support)

		Support for Enhanced Rock Weathering		
Country		ERW Role Addressing Climate Change	ERW Support in Country	ERW Support in Community
Germany	Mean	47.65	50.74	50.09
	N	727	749	741
	Std. Deviation	27.001	26.754	27.419
China	Mean	69.79	69.62	68.13
	N	784	789	784
	Std. Deviation	21.674	22.202	24.255
Brazil	Mean	76.71	73.54	72.39
	N	779	778	777
	Std. Deviation	23.536	26.125	26.458
Kenya	Mean	72.76	75.00	73.90
	N	798	803	801
	Std. Deviation	25.239	26.083	27.330
USA	Mean	65.96	68.15	65.49
	N	763	772	764
	Std. Deviation	27.006	26.856	27.876
Total	Mean	66.87	67.59	66.20
	N	3851	3891	3867
	Std. Deviation	26.826	27.037	27.966

Relative Support for Enhanced rock weathering vis-à-vis Direct air capture

Both enhanced rock weathering and direct air capture received broadly less support than afforestation and reforestation, irrespective of the country or location of activity. We additionally established that enhanced rock weathering often received more support than direct air capture, depending on the country and scale of activities.

Using paired-samples T-testing, we found that enhanced rock weathering received significantly higher support across all three measures in Germany ($p < .001$), with the difference especially pronounced for activities which would be done within one's own community: mean difference=8.172; $t(708) = -6.652$, $p < .001$. In the United States, there was significantly higher support for enhanced rock weathering irrespective of the location of the activity ($p < .001$), though this did not extend to a difference in its perceived role in addressing climate change ($p < .05$).

Meanwhile, in Brazil and Kenya, there was significantly higher support for enhanced rock weathering, though only related to activities done within one's own community: in Kenya, mean difference=2.466; $t(797) = 2.182$, $p = .029$; in Brazil, mean difference=2.466; $t(760) = 2.529$, $p = .012$.

Conversely, in China, there was no significant difference between the level of support for enhanced rock weathering vis-à-vis direct air capture ($p < .05$).

Reasons for Support of Carbon Dioxide Removal Technologies

Having asked participants which of ten reasons – along with an open-ended “other” option – most informed their reasoning to support or not each of the different carbon dioxide removal technologies, we can investigate how these differ both across the three technologies as well as across the five countries. These options were presented (in random order) to participants for each of the technologies, after having been asked to read a short information text and answer the questions about their level of support. Participants could select as many or as few as they found suitable to best reflect their underlying rationales. Accordingly, it is useful to look at the percentage of the sample population which cited a particular reason, both in general and at country level, along with how its frequency relates to the other potential reasons.

In view of the potential to introduce bias here, notably by stipulating overly specific examples and considerations, we opted instead for more general rationales. This list was enumerated through a review of the extant public perceptions research on CDR and to best reflect the kinds of arguments that are most salient in the literature. Indeed, the option of providing overly specific rationales where many participants are quite unfamiliar with CDR technologies was deemed to run the risk of “putting words in the mouth” of participants and facilitating post hoc rationalizations that are more informed and detailed than are likely to exist at present.

Reasons for Support – Direct Air Capture

The reasons for supporting direct air capture also differed markedly in terms of how much they were cited, along with their importance in different countries.

The most common reasons cited for supporting direct air capture (or not) in Germany were: it could have unintended side-effects (59% - highest of any country, tied); would require a lot of resources (energy, land, water, etc.) (53%); or it could threaten humans and nature (43%). Notably these are all more correlated with lack of support, which fits with the relatively low levels of support in Germany. In contrast, the next two most-noted reasons were that direct air capture: can effectively reduce carbon emissions (37%); or can preserve quality of life for future generations (30%).

The most common reasons cited for supporting direct air capture (or not) in China were, in contrast: that it would be environmentally friendly (46%); and can effectively reduce carbon emissions (41%) – as well as can preserve quality of life for future generations (30%) or could create jobs and support economic growth (25%). Notably, these are all more conducive to support for direct air capture. Conversely, a somewhat lower percentage of respondents noted that direct air capture: could have unintended side-effects (35%); and would require a lot of resources (energy, land, water, etc.) (33%).

Meanwhile, the most-cited reasons in Kenya were that direct air capture: can effectively reduce carbon emissions (59% - highest of any country); would be environmentally friendly (46%); can preserve quality of life for future generations (45%); and could create jobs and support economic growth (42%). The latter is by far the highest for any country. At the same time, a significant proportion noted: it would require a lot of resources (energy, land, water,) (42%); could have unintended side-effects (36%); or could threaten humans and nature (33%).

Across the entire sample, the least-highlighted reason for support (or lack thereof) was that direct air capture: would unjustly harm those who are poor (7%); would be an excuse for government involvement (12%); or would decrease the motivation to reduce emissions (15%). The latter is interesting amid the prominent discussion of the potential for “Moral hazard” or “mitigation deterrence” of direct air capture, as well as that this reason was cited least often in Kenya and Brazil (and relatively more often in Germany and China).

Reasons for Support – Afforestation and Reforestation

Reasons for supporting afforestation and reforestation which reflected more positive aspects were generally more prevalent (e.g. vis-à-vis direct air capture). This included a significant majority of the total sample who stated as reasons that afforestation and reforestation: would be environmentally friendly (76%); can preserve quality of life for future generations (70%); and can effectively reduce carbon emissions (68%). Of note, only two other reasons were mentioned by more than 12% of all participants, just one of which cited a negative aspect: could create jobs and support economic growth (35%); and would require a lot of resources (energy, land, water, etc.) (25%).

Nevertheless, there were significant differences at country level. Looking at Kenya, one half of participants cited as a reason that afforestation and reforestation could create jobs and support economic growth (50%), in contrast to one-third or less in the other countries. Those in Kenya were also generally more likely to cite as causes the various positive reasons: would be environmentally friendly (86%); can preserve quality of life for future generations (77%); and can effectively reduce carbon emissions (82%). Regarding the latter reason, the next-closest country percentage was in Germany (75%), though those in Brazil (66%), United States (61%), and China (58%) were all noticeably lower. This reflects a significant disparity in the perceived efficacy of afforestation and reforestation to reduce carbon emissions.

On the flipside, much greater pessimism (relative) is evident in countries such as the United States and China. Participants in both countries were for instance much less likely to cite as a reason that afforestation and reforestation can preserve quality of life for future generations: China (58%); and United States (56%), in contrast to around 80% for the other countries. In addition, participants were noticeably more likely to cite as reasons for their decisions that afforestation and reforestation would require a lot of resources (energy, land, water, etc.): United States (34%) and China (31%) – in sharp contrast to Brazil (13%). Though the overall differences were not as high, those in the United States were more likely to state that afforestation and reforestation could have unintended side-effects (13%), would be an excuse for more government involvement (10%), or could threaten humans and nature (10%) while those in China were more likely to state it would decrease the motivation to reduce emissions (17%).

Reasons for Support – Enhanced Rock Weathering

Reasons for supporting (or not) enhanced rock weathering reflect most participants' prior lack of awareness of this approach and that there is not yet any crystallized opinion. Across the entire sample, the most cited reason was that ERW can effectively reduce carbon emissions (46%) – though given the context of the survey, this could also be an artifact of how the information was presented. At the same time, many other reasons were highlighted by at least one-third of participants, including more positive ones such as would be environmentally friendly (39%) and can preserve quality of life for future generations (38%) and more risk-focused ones such as would require a lot of resources (energy, land, water, etc.) (40%) and could have unintended side-effects (37%). It is worth noting that there was limited concern that enhanced rock weathering would decrease the motivation to reduce emissions (13%); would be an excuse for more government involvement (13%); or would unjustly harm those who are poor (7%).

At country level, however, some significant differences emerge. For instance, more than half of German participants – who were on average the most negative about enhanced rock weathering, cited as reasons that this approach could have unintended

side-effects (61%) and would require a lot of resources (52%). There was also a significantly higher percentage of individuals, compared to other countries, who noted it can threaten humans and nature (36%) – at least 10% more than any other country.

Conversely, Kenya participants were more likely to cite as reasons for their decisions that enhanced rock weathering both can effectively reduce carbon emissions (60%) – at least 14% more than any other country – and could create jobs and support economic growth (46%) – at least 15% more than the second-highest percentage (in Brazil). Rather than overly optimistic though, Kenya also had among the highest percentage of participants who thought that enhanced rock weathering could threaten humans and nature (26%) and the highest about whether it would be an excuse for more government involvement (13%) or would unjustly harm those who are poor (10%). The differences here are not of as large of a magnitude as the other reasons, but they are important to demonstrate the kinds of concerns which enhanced rock weathering must manage even among participants who are relatively more positive.

It is also worth noting that Brazilian participants, despite expressing among the highest support for enhanced rock weathering, were not necessarily likely to cite any particular reasons for doing so – at least in a way that diverged from the average from the total sample. There is a slightly higher percentage who noted that it can preserve quality of life for future generations (45%, versus sample average of 38%). But it is rather in the relative absence of specific concerns which stands out, notably that enhanced rock weathering would require a lot of resources (30%, versus sample average of 40%); otherwise, it is similar to the other countries, except Germany.

Support for Environmental Policies

Here we focus on the descriptive statistics and the relative (mean) support for 12 environmental policies across the five countries (see Table 5). The most-supported policies across the entire sample were (1) increasing protections on forested and natural grassland areas (M=88.84) and (2) strengthening laws to keep waterways and oceans clean (87.25), both in the category of “nature protection” – which also were the policies with fewest “No Opinion” responses. Then came “mitigation” type activities, principally using a more investment-focused approach, such as (3) investing in more renewable energy sources such as wind and solar (84.84), (4) investing more in green jobs and businesses, and (5) expanding infrastructure for bicycling and public transportation (81.90).

Table 5: Support for twelve Environmental policies across countries (0-100 scale, 0=strongly oppose, 100=strongly support)

		Support for Environmental Policies											
Country		Increasing taxes on gas, fossil fuels, and coal	Expanding infrastructure for bicycling and public transportation	Increasing the number of charging stations for electric vehicles	Investing more in renewable energy sources such as wind and solar	Increasing taxes on carbon emissions of airline companies	Increasing protections on forested and natural grassland areas	Investing more in green jobs and businesses	Strengthening laws to keep waterways and oceans clean	Increasing taxes on foods with high carbon emissions (for example meat and dairy)	Investing more in technologies that remove carbon dioxide from the air	Making green energy the default in energy contracts	Informing households of how their energy consumption compares to their neighbors
Germany	Mean	45.45	77.61	65.67	77.96	64.32	88.62	72.95	84.40	45.40	70.34	70.47	48.72
	N	784	797	767	796	784	809	776	804	794	786	778	749
	Std. Deviation	31.269	23.164	28.914	25.017	31.052	15.078	23.447	17.971	32.137	23.394	27.554	32.426
China	Mean	69.08	82.20	77.82	83.02	72.89	87.41	83.04	84.09	65.18	76.71	78.85	70.45
	N	789	797	786	794	785	798	794	797	778	790	788	782
	Std. Deviation	22.451	14.201	16.777	14.575	18.950	11.949	13.205	14.003	24.255	16.495	16.374	21.534
Brazil	Mean	55.19	87.66	82.67	92.34	71.70	91.72	90.19	91.55	51.92	87.19	86.58	71.43
	N	779	795	783	799	780	798	794	798	780	793	791	772
	Std. Deviation	33.452	16.682	20.239	13.289	29.985	13.566	14.402	14.318	34.738	17.666	17.826	28.548
Kenya	Mean	64.02	86.74	86.04	93.88	77.10	94.21	90.61	93.83	59.12	87.97	85.45	75.18
	N	786	795	795	804	791	802	799	802	791	800	796	784
	Std. Deviation	32.221	18.632	20.891	11.795	26.342	11.072	15.010	10.730	32.788	18.840	18.474	26.724
USA	Mean	55.82	75.22	66.83	76.86	66.38	82.16	75.69	82.39	52.12	75.05	71.32	70.50
	N	776	783	762	790	763	794	776	796	772	779	761	765
	Std. Deviation	31.727	22.247	28.476	24.115	28.231	18.883	23.898	18.571	31.964	23.085	26.031	26.022
Total	Mean	57.94	81.90	75.93	84.85	70.51	88.84	82.58	87.26	54.73	79.50	78.63	67.39
	N	3914	3967	3893	3983	3903	4001	3939	3997	3915	3948	3914	3852
	Std. Deviation	31.518	19.870	24.878	19.911	27.614	14.934	19.888	16.039	32.103	21.245	22.708	28.779

Then came (6) investing more in technologies that remove carbon dioxide from the air (79.50), potentially benefitting from the focus of the survey, followed by (7) making green energy the default in energy contracts, which was an example of a behavioural “nudge”-style approach.

After these policies, there were (8) increasing the number of charging stations for electric vehicles (M=75.92), which received significantly less support than supporting infrastructure e.g. for bicycling and public transportation, and (9) increasing taxes on carbon emissions of airline companies (70.51), which was the first of the tax-employing policies. Interestingly, the former received higher support than (10) informing households of how their energy consumption compares to their neighbours, the other of the “nudge” style approaches.

Receiving the relatively lowest support by some margin were (11) increasing taxes on gas, fossil fuels, and coal (M=57.94) and (12) increasing taxes on foods with high carbon emissions (for example meat and dairy) (54.72).

It is worth remarking that there is at least some level of support for all options, which can only reflect some degree of positivity bias – to note, the initial scale was from -50 (strongly oppose) to +50 (strongly support). Participants might have been less willing to make use of the negative part of the scale, or to select “no opinion” here if in any doubt, which is why it is crucial to stress that the above means are after participants selecting “no opinion” were removed (out of necessity) – though at most the percentage of “no opinion” responses was never higher than 4%. These numbers are thus likely to under-estimate the level of opposition which might be encountered by some of these policies, as real-world evidence for carbon taxes has demonstrated.

Difference in support for environmental policies across countries

In addition to the relative preference among the different policies, the differences in the level of support which policies garner across countries also deserves attention. As an example, German participants were significantly more negative about informing households of how their consumption compares to their neighbours (M=48.72) than other countries (all above 70.00). This was not the case for the other nudge-style policy – making green energy the default in energy contracts – though this received much higher support in Brazil (86.58) and Kenya (85.45) than in more developed countries.

While there was a relative dis-preference for the use of taxes, the type of tax that was more problematic differed across countries. Those in Brazil are noticeably more negative about increasing taxes on foods with high carbon emissions (M=51.92), which makes sense given the importance of meat and dairy for their economic sector. Those in the United States and especially Germany were less positive about taxes on

gas, fossil fuels, and coal and/or taxes on high-carbon foods – less so taxes on carbon emissions of airline companies. Meanwhile, those in China, and to some extent Kenya, seemed to offer less opposition in general to taxes: this often amounted to fifteen to twenty points greater support for taxes on gas, fossil fuels and coal or taxes on foods with high carbon emissions than other countries, notably Germany. A similar pattern was evident for increasing the number of charging stations, with support fifteen to twenty points higher in Kenya and Brazil vis-à-vis Germany and the United States – which could also reflect greater understanding on the part of participants in the latter of the real-world demands of such a policy.

One special mention about the relative support for investments into carbon dioxide removal technologies. Such support was significantly higher in Kenya (M=87.97) and Brazil (M=87.19) vis-à-vis China (M=76.68), the United States (M=75.05), and Germany (M=70.34). For Kenya, this was the fifth-highest level of support of any policy – closely followed by expanding infrastructure for bicycling and public transportation or increasing the number of charging stations for electric vehicles. For Brazil, this was sixth highest, after expanding infrastructure for bicycling and public transportation and above making green energy the default in energy contracts. While it received the seventh-highest level of support in the United States and Germany (albeit very close to the sixth-highest option: making green energy the default in energy contracts), a CDR investment policy received only the eighth-highest support in China.

While no direct trade-offs between the different policies were elicited, the results do paint a picture, at an aggregate level, of investment policy in CDR being far from the most-preferred policy option. At the same time, we find CDR investments to be viewed more positively than the least preferred options, notably taxes. In this respect, a broad preference ordering emerges wherein investments in CDR share a broad space with other policies such as increasing the number of charging stations for electric vehicles and making green energy the default in energy contracts.

To further investigate these differences in general and at country level, subsequent analyses will also draw on responses to two questions which asked participants how much the (i) effectiveness and (ii) fairness of the various climate policies informed their respective levels of support. Together with the additional survey responses, e.g. regarding beliefs and perceptions related to climate change (see below), these will be used to gain further insight into the varying support of the set of environmental policies.

Beliefs and Perceptions Related to Climate Change across Countries

To identify how participants and countries differed in terms of their beliefs and perceptions related to climate change, we asked eight questions in total. The first of these related to the belief that climate change is occurring and the extent to which it is

mostly the result of human activity, respectively. There were also questions about how worried participants were about climate change, its perceived importance for them personally, how much they expected to be harmed personally by climate change, and then the extent to which they perceived it to be a government priority, or how much they felt a moral obligation to help reduce climate change.

As an initial step, we have analysed differences in climate beliefs and perceptions at a country level. Subsequent analyses will examine their role as explanatory variables in relation to the levels of support for CDR technologies and/or environmental policies

Beliefs in Climate Change

Using a 1-5 scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5), we identified significantly less agreement that climate change is occurring (according to chi-squared testing) in the United States than other countries, particularly Brazil and Kenya (see Figure 1). Ultimately, the number of participants disagreeing about the existence of climate change was less than 7% in the United States, and under 5% in Germany and Kenya. Participants in China were also more likely to simply “agree” rather than “strongly agree” to this question, which differed from the other countries.

Figure 1: Belief that Climate Change is Occurring, across Countries (1-5 scale)

Similarly, disagreement that climate change is mostly due to human activity was substantially higher in the United States (12%) followed by Germany (9.0%). In contrast, the level of agreement in Brazil and Kenya was equal to 89.9% and 93.0%,

respectively, versus 81.9% in China (again with more participants expressing agreement versus strong agreement), 73.1% in USA and 78.5% in Germany.

Figure 2: Belief that Climate Change is mostly the result of Human Activity, across Countries (1-5 scale)

Worry about Climate Change and Perceptions of Climate Change

Significantly greater worry about climate change was expressed in Brazil and Kenya, with 78.6% in Kenya and 81.4% in Brazil expressing that they are very or extremely worried (see Table 6 for country-level means across all climate perceptions variables) – compared to 56.6% in Germany, 54.2% in USA, and 53.1% in China. In contrast, 18.6% in the USA, 15.7% in Germany, and 8.9% in China expressed that they were not too worried or not at all worried.

There was a similar pattern as for climate change worry, with Brazil and Kenya placing greater personal importance on climate change. There was one exception: those in the United States placed greater importance in Germany (with China in the middle).

Expected personal harm from climate change was also significantly higher in Kenya (M=4.03) and Brazil (M=3.88), followed by China (M=3.45) and the United States (M=3.25), and then Germany (M=3.19), according to independent-samples Kruskal-Wallis H testing, $H(4)=373.726, p<.001$.

As for the other climate variables, there is the similar pattern of Kenyan participants identifying climate change as a government priority (90.8% high or very high), followed by Brazil (86.4% high or very high), followed by China (82.0%), and then the United

States (67.2%) and Germany (67.3%) (see Figure 3). Of note, 12.8% in the United States and 10.7% in Germany identified climate change as a low or very low priority for the government.

Table 5: Country-level means related to worry about climate change and perceptions of climate change (all variables 1-5 scale, labels differ)

Country		Worry and Perceptions about Climate Change				
		Worry about Climate Change	Personal Importance of Climate Change	Personal Harm from Climate Change	Climate Change as Government Priority	Moral Obligation about Climate Change
Germany	Mean	3.57	3.44	3.19	3.84	3.64
	N	809	809	809	809	809
	Std. Deviation	1.069	1.051	1.083	1.065	1.133
China	Mean	3.57	3.59	3.45	4.11	4.17
	N	801	801	801	801	801
	Std. Deviation	.852	.977	.968	.765	.767
Brazil	Mean	4.20	4.24	3.88	4.37	4.18
	N	801	801	801	801	801
	Std. Deviation	.854	.863	1.061	.864	.902
Kenya	Mean	4.14	4.31	4.03	4.55	4.37
	N	804	804	804	804	804
	Std. Deviation	.825	.730	.873	.729	.993
USA	Mean	3.56	3.60	3.25	3.85	3.74
	N	800	800	800	800	800
	Std. Deviation	1.200	1.190	1.293	1.161	1.096
Total	Mean	3.81	3.83	3.56	4.14	4.02
	N	4015	4015	4015	4015	4015
	Std. Deviation	1.016	1.041	1.116	.973	1.026

When it came to moral obligation to help reduce climate change, Kenyan participants also agreed that they had such an obligation (90.0% agree or strongly agree). For this question, there was however no significant difference between Chinese (87.2% agree or strongly agree) and Brazilian participants (82.3%). Once again, those in the United States (65.4%) and Germany (65.4%) perceived such a moral obligation much less strongly. Meanwhile, 16.1% in Germany and 12.0% in the USA disagreed that they felt such a moral obligation.

Figure 3: Perception of Climate Change as a Government Priority, across Countries (1-5 scale)

Conclusion

The survey examined perceptions and support of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies (enhanced rock weathering, direct air capture, afforestation and reforestation) along with support of twelve climate policies across 5 countries (United States, Brazil, Kenya, Germany, and China), along with identifying key determinants that related to support and perceptions. Surveys were nationally representative, with N=800 participants in each country) in terms of age, gender, income, educational attainment, geographic region, and geographic area, i.e. urban versus rural.

First, we note that familiarity is quite low across participants and across all countries regarding direct air capture and enhanced rock weathering – though higher in the case of afforestation and reforestation (though less so in the United States). We also identified significant differences (according to nonparametric testing) in the level of support for carbon dioxide removal technologies across all countries. In general, the participants in Brazil and Kenya expressed higher support on average for all the technologies. In contrast, Germany was the least supportive for both direct air capture and enhanced rock weathering, though with the third-highest level of support for afforestation and reforestation. Participants in China were more positive than those in the United States about direct air capture, though their level of support did not differ for the other two technologies.

Regarding relative preferences among the three technologies, the level of support of afforestation and reforestation was still significantly higher than either direct air capture or enhanced rock weathering across all countries (according to paired-samples t-testing). This was true, irrespective of the country or location of activity. We also established that enhanced rock weathering often received more support than direct air capture, depending on the country and scale of activities. This was most consistently the case in Germany and the United States, while enhanced rock weathering was only significantly preferred in Brazil and Kenya when it was to be done within one's own community. No such differences could be found for China.

We also identified differences in level of support depending on the location of the activity, that is if it were to be done broadly in one's country or within one's own community. In all countries except Germany, we find a significantly higher level of support (according to paired-samples t-testing) if direct air capture or enhanced rock weathering were developed and deployed in the country rather than within one's own community. There was less of a difference regarding afforestation and reforestation, though we find a small but significant decrease in level of support in Brazil and China if afforestation and reforestation were to happen within their own communities.

Having asked participants which reasons most informed their decision to support or not each of the different carbon dioxide removal technologies, we could also gain insights here into how the reasons varied across technologies and between countries. Regarding direct air capture, for instance, the most common reasons cited in Germany were typically about potential risks, such as that it could have unintended side-effects, would require a lot of resources, or could threaten humans and nature. This fits with the relative negativity in Germany about direct air capture. In Kenya, in contrast, the most-cited reasons were about potential opportunities, such as the ability to effectively reduce carbon emissions; it would be environmentally friendly; can preserve quality of life for future generations; and could create jobs and support economic growth. Meanwhile, the reasons for supporting (or not) enhanced rock weathering best reflect the fact that most participants lacked prior awareness of this approach and that there is not yet any crystallized opinion. Overall, the reasons that were cited related to afforestation and reforestation were much more focused on more positive aspects vis-a-vis other technologies – this provides an echo of the findings for support.

Having asked about support for twelve different environmental policies, we established that the most-supported policies across the entire sample related to "nature protection" (i.e. increasing protections on forested areas, strengthening laws to keep oceans clean). Those receiving the next-most support entailed investments in "mitigation", such as in renewables or to expand public transport infrastructure. Those receiving by far the least support involved taxes, notably on gas and fossil fuels or

foods with high carbon emissions (e.g. meat or dairy). Given that investments in carbon dioxide removal technologies were one of the twelve options, we could also identify a middling level of support for this option – receiving the fifth- to eighth-highest level of support, depending on the country. This illustrates that CDR investments are far from the most-preferred policy option, alongside other policies such as increasing the number of charging stations for electric vehicles and making green energy the default in energy contracts.

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3. Regional implications of noncooperative stratospheric aerosol injection

Introduction

In a world of insufficient mitigation efforts and with increasing evidence suggesting high impacts from climate change even under accelerated action¹, discussions around geoengineering are intensifying. Geoengineering techniques could provide a valuable addition to the basket of tools available to reduce climate impacts and their socio-economic ramifications. Among them, Stratospheric Aerosol Injection (SAI) is the most discussed because of its expected low costs and historical analogues providing evidence for its global effectiveness. Efficacy and effectiveness, however, might not be the most relevant dimension when it comes to SAI (or other forms of geoengineering). Because multiple injection strategies are possible², strong governance is fundamental to any meaningful deployment. How much and at which latitudes SAI is deployed might dramatically shape the map of winners and losers, and thus of the desirability, of climate interventions. The injection strategy is ultimately determined by who, and to whose benefits, deploys SAI: a global benevolent planner would tailor a strategy aimed to minimize global suffering, but self-interested nations might have little interest in minimizing temperature impacts or reducing SAI side-effects outside of their borders.

Putting international climate dilemmas at the center of analysis³, it is therefore crucial to capture the regional impacts of different deployment strategies to adequately represent the sweeping possibility space of SAI scenarios. Current assessments of climate or climate-economy models, however, largely fail to capture the interaction between the physical characteristics of SAI and its governance, mostly depicting

benign scenarios of idealized, global interventions. Here, we try to fill this gap by linking an earth system model (ESM) emulator to a country-level integrated assessment model (IAM). We use this tool to explore the physical and welfare impacts of SAI deployed both under either a cooperative regime or unilaterally by four representative egoistic actors (US, China, India, Brazil).

Ultimately, large discrepancies in SAI strategies designed by different actors emerge because the physical and economic impacts of SAI and climate change vary across time and space. In our modelling framework, we capture regional heterogeneity in three ways. First, the regional pattern of cooling provided by SAI is roughly uniform across longitudes but is highly dependent on the injection latitude^{4,5}. For instance, SAI in the Southern Hemisphere (SH) cools SH countries more than Northern Hemisphere (NH) ones (and vice versa). Second, side-effects of regional interventions are unevenly distributed: asymmetric injection strategies can have large effects on precipitation in equatorial and tropical regions, mainly because they shift the intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ) which drives monsoons patterns⁶. Finally, empirical evidence from past data^{1,7-9} suggest that the economic impacts of temperature variation vary across countries, with equatorial and tropical countries particularly at risk.

Despite the relevance of these geographical patterns for both physical and economic implications of climate engineering, the existing literature has mostly neglected them. A part of the game-theoretical literature in economics recognizes the possible regional asymmetry of cooling preferences, injection strategy, and side-effects^{10,11}. However, numerical climate-economic model assessments have not considered these dimensions together. Some include heterogeneous preferences and impacts of temperature variation^{12,13} in the context of stylized or cooperative deployment of SAI. Only a few consider this heterogeneity in non-cooperative or coalitional scenarios^{14,15}. The side effects of geoengineering are usually included as a global function¹⁶⁻¹⁸, with few exceptions that explicitly considers regional economic impacts from precipitation variations due to SAI in the context of a coalition formation game¹⁵ or in a cost risk analysis framework¹⁹. In all these works, however, the injection strategy is implicitly or explicitly tailored to minimize the differences between the climates of the scenarios with SAI and without (but with the same global forcing), because they are calibrated from climate model simulations that feature either idealized experiments of uniform reduction of the solar constant²⁰, or symmetric tropical injection. In this sense, SAI is idealized in this literature even when discussing non-cooperative injections, and an integration of the recent advancements in the climate modelling literature is lacking^{2,4,6}.

Here, we advance the fast-growing literature on climate-economic modelling of solar geoengineering by explicitly representing latitudinal interventions and their physical

and economic repercussions under different scenarios of international cooperation. To endogenize the choice of deploying SAI and its consequences on local temperature, precipitation and consequently on economic wellbeing, we propose a high-resolution modelling framework integrating earth system and climate-economy modelling.

Characterizing latitudinal SAI and its climate impacts

We start from an established, open-source coupled climate-economy model ²¹ (available at <https://github.com/witch-team/RICE50xmodel>) downscaled at the country-level. We add injection location and amount as decision variables to the optimization problem (see Methods for details). We couple the model to an emulator based on ⁶ reproducing the cooling and precipitation effects of injection of stratospheric sulphur at different latitudes (60S to 60N every 15° of latitude). The emulator is calibrated using a statistical model from a set of single injection scenarios of 12 Tg-SO₂ using CESM2-WACCM6, assuming linearity in the climate outcomes between different injection locations (as verified in ²²). The grid-level results of the mean of the model ensemble are upscaled at the country level with population weighting (see Methods for details).

The emulator captures the variation in the physical consequences of SAI depending on the injection latitude (see Figure 1 for three representative injection latitudes 30N-0-30S). Northern hemisphere injection (yellow line and dots) cools the north more than the south, and decreases (increases) annual mean precipitation for northern (southern) tropical countries. Vice versa (blue lines and dots), southern injection cools more and reduces precipitation in southern hemisphere countries. Equatorial injection (green line and dots) produces a pattern of cooling more resemblant of the effects of emission reductions for an equivalent amount of avoided global warming (dotted black line), and more contained – but not negligible – precipitation disruptions.

Figure 1. Outcomes of the climate emulator for temperature and precipitation. (a) temperature decrease for each country (dots) mapped by their average latitude for different injection latitudes (colours) for an injection of 12 Tg-SO₂/yr relative to the SSP2 4.5 baseline climate. (b) precipitation variation for each country (dots) mapped by their average latitude for different injection latitudes (colours) for an injection of 12 TgS/yr, expressed as number of standard deviations relative to the historical country mean over the period 1990-2014. Coloured lines identify the population-weighted median response per latitude and injection latitude across countries. Dotted black dots indicate the pattern of cooling/precipitation variations obtained with emission reductions leading to an equivalent amount of avoided global warming. Grey band area identifies variations in precipitation below +/- 1 standard deviation of historical variability.

Both temperature and precipitation changes from global warming and SAI affect economic activity through impact functions based on empirical studies on the historical relationship between variation of temperature and precipitation and economic growth. The impact function for temperature features heterogeneous preferences for preferred regional temperature and heterogeneous damages from temperature variation across countries, characteristics found consistently in the climate econometric literature^{1,7,8,23}. The intensity of the temperature-driven economic impacts is calibrated on Burke et al.⁷ (Methods). The intensity of precipitation impacts is calibrated on Kotz et al.²⁴ (Methods), and we conservatively assume that each country is adapted to its historical precipitation levels and that any variation in precipitations causes economic harm (Methods). We test these assumptions by varying the intensity for precipitation impacts and assuming diverging preferences for regional preferred annual precipitations²⁵. In line with the most recent evidence¹, climate impacts persist for 10 years for temperature impacts

and 5 years for precipitation impacts (see Methods for our representation of persistency).

While not explicitly modelled, other characteristics of SAI other than temperature and precipitation effects can impact economic output and welfare. We include them through scenario assumptions of SAI deployments. First, we consider a constraint on maximum temperature variation of at most 0.3°C per decade^{26,27} to avoid abrupt scale-up of SAI that could cause catastrophic effects on the climate and biosphere. Second, we assume across all scenarios a temporary deployment of SAI with a total phase-out imposed by the year 2200, to account for other side-effects of geoengineering such as cumulative sulphur deposition²⁸, that have been shown to be moderate⁵ but could compound to relevant levels in a multi century-scale deployment.

Scenario Design

In this study, we are interested in assessing the physical and economic impacts of latitudinal SAI interventions under different international cooperation regimes. We start from an idealized scenario where SAI (starting from 2035) and mitigation are deployed, wherever is needed, to maximize global welfare (SAI + mitigation). To quantify the value of full cooperation on SAI, we contrast it with a counterfactual scenario of full cooperation only on emissions reductions (mitigation scenario). In our framework, which reflects the high economic risks of climate change, this is coherent with a scenario compatible with the 2°C target of the Paris agreement.

Then, we analyse four scenarios of non-cooperation with four different unilateral deployers (USA, China, India, and Brazil). In each scenario, only one country is allowed to deploy, and no international cooperation is assumed on mitigation, resulting in continued global emissions throughout the century. We restrict the analysis to these four countries because of their heterogeneous geographical characteristics and because of constraints over deployment capabilities that restrict likely deployers to a handful of powerful actors²⁹. To recognize different levels of technological preparedness, USA and China can start injecting in 2035, while India and Brazil in 2050.

Cooperative Development

We first analyse two scenarios of full global cooperation, comparing the case without and with SAI to assess the potential role of an internationally coordinated, regional climate engineering strategy aimed at the global good. When countries cooperate on emission reductions, temperatures are kept below 2°C at all latitudes except the arctic circle (Figure 2a). This result confirms the economic rationale of the Paris agreement, in line with recent developments in cost-benefit analysis³⁰⁻³². Average precipitations

remain within historical ranges. Nonetheless, the economic damages of residual warming are significant for equatorial and tropical countries, with losses exceeding 10% of GDP at the end of the century (Figure 2c). This result is consistent with the high recent estimates of the economic damages of even moderate warming^{1,30}, to which the model is calibrated. These concerns provide a possible global rationale for geoengineering, which allows reducing temperatures beyond what emission reductions can do and thus help minimize residual climate change impacts.

Figure 2. Physical and economic implications of full global cooperation on mitigation and mitigation + SAI across latitudes. (a) latitudinal temperature increase in 2100 relative to pre-industrial. The dashed black line shows the economically-preferred temperature profile (b) precipitation variation in 2100 relative to pre-industrial baseline (c) total GDP loss in 2100. In panels b-d each point represents a country, positioned at their average latitude, and lines represent population weighted best-fits trend lines for each scenario.

To reach this objective, the total amount of SAI injected globally increases over time to reaches 25 TgS/yr at the end of the century, which roughly corresponds to 2°C of average land surface cooling. A part of this cooling masks the underlying warming due to the crowding out of emission reduction by SAI (around 0.5 °C). The exact amount of substitution between emission reductions and SAI depends on several scenario assumptions, especially the termination year for SAI. Most of the cooling (1.5 °C) pushes global temperature below the levels reached with emission reductions alone. A desirable implementation strategy of this magnitude must lower global temperature without causing excessive shifts in precipitation patterns or intensity, obtained via roughly symmetrical north-south injection. Our model finds that the preferred latitudes for injections are 15 and 45 N/S, because subtropical injection causes the highest shift in precipitation.

Such a coordinated SAI strategy would allow cooling down all regions one to two degrees more than achieved in the mitigation scenario (Figure 2a, blue line and dots below green line and dots) and closer to the preferred temperature for each region (Figure 2a, black dotted line and dots). Precipitation variations are larger than in the mitigation scenario but remain mostly contained below one standard deviation of historical variability. Overall, the benefits of globally coordinated cooling and, to a lower extent, avoided mitigation costs result in large welfare gains for all countries. Equatorial and tropical countries benefit the most from cooperative geoengineering implementation, confirming previous literature that disregarded precipitation impacts¹².

Average precipitation remains within historical record. Annual precipitation does not necessarily capture extremes or seasonal pattern changes, potentially non-negligible for monsoonal regions. However, previous research found they would also be compensated by a symmetric SAI strategy³³.

Notably, the trade-off arising between containing precipitation variations and optimizing for temperature results in undercooling of equatorial and tropical regions (Figure 2a, blue line above dotted black line) and overcooling of high latitude countries (Figure 2a, blue line below dotted black line) relative to their preferred temperature. Therefore, moderate residual impacts add up to remaining mitigation effort in the mitigation + SAI scenario (max 5% of baseline GDP, blue line in Figure 2c). Overcooling of high latitude countries is accentuated under higher heterogeneity of preferred temperature across countries. Under low precipitation impacts, the injection strategy remains largely symmetrical but the reduced trade-off between climatic objectives leads to more injections on the tropics. Residual impacts are, therefore, further reduced. With asymmetrical preferences for wetting and drying further gains can be realized by injecting more sulphur in the southern than in the northern hemisphere, which results in increased precipitations in northern tropical and equatorial countries.

Overall, a coordinated SAI strategy for the global good would be beneficial, especially in most at-risk countries in the tropics and equator. The trade-offs of climate objectives (here reduced to mean temperature and precipitation) appear to be manageable across the specifications tested with adjustments in the intensity and location of interventions.

Costs of unilateral deployment

The world, however, is very far from fully cooperative. If countries with the ability to deploy geoengineering were to do so without considering the welfare of people outside their borders, they could cause significant harm. In our setting, impacts from unilateral deployment stem from two channels. First, the unilateral deployer will choose how much to cool depending on its needed, thus under/over cooling the remaining regions. Second, an egoistic injection strategy can cause large precipitation variations outside the border of the deployer. Furthermore, these impacts are exacerbated by the lack of cooperation on mitigation that increases the underlying radiative forcing and climate risks relative to the cooperative scenarios analysed above.

The different geographical characteristics of our four representative countries result in varied injection strategies. Tropical and equatorial countries (Brazil and India) inject 30 and 29 TgS/yr respectively in 2100, 20% more than in the mitigation + SAI cooperative scenario. These countries deploy in their respective hemispheres (19 TGS/yr at 30S for Brazil, 16 TgS/yr at 15N for India) counterbalanced by equatorial (13 TgS/yr at the equator for India) or opposite hemisphere (11 TGS/yr at 15N for Brazil) injection to minimize precipitation trade-offs within their borders. On the contrary, mid-latitude countries (China and the US) inject 16 TgS/yr in 2100, a reduction of 40% relative to the mitigation + SAI scenario. All the deployment happens in the northern hemisphere (15N for China, 45N for USA) because these countries are minimally affected by precipitation variations at that level of deployment. While we don't constrain the deployment latitude to be strictly within national borders, it should be noted that accessing the opposite hemisphere would be logistically, diplomatically and militarily challenging in case of unilateral deployment¹¹. Restricting injection latitudes to sovereign territory would result in higher trade-offs within and across the borders of the implementing country, exacerbating the impacts described below for the Brazil scenario. We now analyse these effects of these strategies both in their physical magnitude (Figure 3) and in their economic consequences (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Physical consequences of unilateral deployment. (a) deviation from preferred temperature (black dots in Figure 2) in °C and (b) variation of precipitation expressed as standard deviations relative to historical mean (preferred variation is zero for all countries) for all SAI implementation scenarios. For unilateral SAI scenarios, the deploying country is marked with red lines. The scales are discretized with the following nomenclature (referring to absolute values). Extreme: [$>1^{\circ}\text{C}$] or [>2 std]. Significant: [$1-0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$] or [$1-2$ std]. Moderate: [$0.5-0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$] or [$1-0.2$ std]. No variation: [$<0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$] or [<0.2 std]. Bubbles represent the deployment latitudes for each scenario. The size of the bubble is proportional to the amount injected for each latitude.

Figure 4. Economic consequences of unilateral deployment. (a) countries mapped for each scenario according to their ranking of preferred scenarios: laissez faire identifies the countries that are better off with non-cooperative deployment of that particular country relative to cooperative deployment. Push to cooperation identifies the countries that are better off with cooperative SAI deployment than with non-cooperative deployment. Push to mitigation identifies the countries that are better off in the 2°C scenario relative to the non-cooperative deployment. Bottom bars represent the % of global population in 2100 that supports each strategy (b) median difference across countries belonging to the same latitude group (equatorial, tropical, subtropical, high latitudes) of the GDP losses (coloured bar) between each non-cooperative scenario (rows identify the deployer) and the cooperative deployment of SAI, normalized with the difference of costs between the cooperative deployment of SAI scenario and the 2°C scenario. Different shades identify different source of cost/gain variation (temperature impacts, precipitation impacts, and mitigation costs). Points and line range identify the median (population weighted) and the confidence interval of the normalized cost difference across countries belonging to the same latitude group.

From the previous section, we know that the Cooperative scenario (first column of Figure 3) entails a moderate, but visible trade-off between optimization of temperature

preferences and containment of precipitation variations, which results in moderate overcooling of the northern and undercooling of the southern hemisphere.

When either India or Brazil deploy, the pattern of cooling largely resembles the mitigation + SAI scenario, with local differences such as more undercooling of northern Europe or overcooling of Australia (for India as deployer), and larger overcooling of Canada (for Brazil as deployer). However, unilateral action has major repercussions for precipitations: large reductions (2 to 3 standard deviations of 1990-2010 historical average) are imposed to sub-Saharan Africa, central America and south-east Asia – especially with India as a deployer.

Egoistic deployment from temperate countries (China and US) results in massive undercooling of the entirety of the southern hemisphere, and moderate to significant undercooling for most of the northern one as well. Because of lower injections and lack of emission reduction, precipitation variations are lower with mid-latitude deployers, but sub-Saharan countries, India, and central America still face significant reductions in precipitation, especially for China, which injects at the tropics.

These complex physical patterns generate heterogeneous economic impacts (Figure 4). Differences in GDP loss across scenarios stem from temperature and precipitation damages but also from variations of emission reduction expenditures across scenarios. To assess them, we divide the costs of unilateral deployment (i.e. the GDP losses stemming from unilateral versus cooperative deployment of SAI) by the value of cooperative deployment (the GDP gains from a cooperative scenario with and without SAI). Countries can then be classified into three groups (Figure 4a), depending on this ratio being negative, between 0 and 1, or above 1: those that prefer unilateral implementation of a certain deployer (*laissez-faire*, blue areas in Figure 4a and values below 0% in Figure 4b); those that prefer the cooperative mitigation + SAI scenario to unilateral implementation, but not the mitigation scenario (push to cooperation, white areas Figure 4a and values between 0-100% in Figure 4b); those that prefer not only the cooperative mitigation+ SAI scenario, but also the mitigation scenario (non-use, red areas in Figure 4a and values above 100% in Figure 4b). Non-use countries could support a non-use agreement and demand high mitigation efforts to edge the risks of geoengineering misuse³⁴.

For Brazil and India as deployers, a global majority favours the *laissez-faire* approach. However, equatorial and tropical countries would face significant impacts, mainly due to precipitations (light purple and blue bars in Figure 4b).

A north- south divide arises if China and the US deploy. Most countries below the tropic of Capricorn face high damages from misused SAI, mainly due to temperature for equatorial countries (dark purple bars in Figure 4b) and equally due to temperature and precipitations for tropical countries (dark-light blue bars in Figure 4b). For these

regions, damages are on average 2-3 times higher than the residual impacts of a 2°C scenario (point and line ranges). In these scenarios, only 20% of the global population would support the unilateral implementation, and, for the US as deployer, a global majority would face higher impacts than in the mitigation scenario.

If precipitation impacts are assumed low, the related impacts are obviously reduced, but the strategy of all unilateral deployers remains consistent. In the rest of the specifications considered, injection strategy and impacts are consistent. Therefore, the damages of unilateral deployment from the US and China – mainly driven from temperature - are robust to the precipitation and temperature impact specifications.

Discussion

Several considerations emerge from the complex interplay between international governance and regionally differentiated impacts of climate interventions.

First, good governance is the most relevant factor to ensure a desirable SAI deployment. Cooperative SAI is always welfare improving and non-cooperative strategies cause large regional adverse effects for all tested assumptions about deploying actors, impacts, and preferences. The only relevant exception is unilateral deployment from tropical countries with low precipitation impacts, which produces GDP losses comparable to cooperative SAI.

Second, equatorial and tropical regions with more to gain from a cooperative deployment of SAI also have more to lose from its misuse. These regions are also the poorest and less equipped to adapt to mutating environmental conditions, as well as the least responsible for past and future emissions. Third, northern hemisphere countries benefit from geoengineering even when deployed unilaterally by hot countries. These benefits don't come from reduced suffering from climate impacts, that temperate and rich nation are less affected by, but mainly from forsaking mitigation efforts. This suggests that these countries are most vulnerable to mitigation deterrence, and they could be lenient in accepting a foreign power deploying SAI if it licenses postponing emission reductions, even at the cost of large impacts elsewhere.

Finally, the risks of overcooling the northern hemisphere exist but it is a lesser consequence of geoengineering misuse, because rich northern hemisphere countries are less affected by climate change. On the contrary, it is the combination of under-provision of geoengineering in the global south under high GHGs emissions, and/or large precipitation variations due to highly asymmetric injection strategies, that poses the largest threats.

While countries like India could cause significant damages if they deployed unilaterally, these considerations suggest that the most dangerous unilateral deployers would be temperate, northern hemisphere countries like US and China, that – if acting as purely egoistic agents - would not be incentivized to provide adequate cooling to the global south, nor to minimize shifts of monsoon patterns they are not affected by. To reinforce the concern, these countries could also more easily develop the necessary technology and effortlessly sustain the costs of deployment.

These considerations bring nuance to the claim that SAI could reduce international inequality ¹². Our results confirm this finding only in a highly idealized future: under pessimistic governance assumptions, powerful states can severely damage less developed regions. Of course, a large set of relevant possibilities exists between perfect cooperation and pure non-cooperation. A self-interested country that develops the technology for SAI first could deter other countries from doing so, maintaining control of the regional and global thermostat. Alternatively, they might also negotiate a compromise deployment to reap the double dividend of gaining political influence and sharing the costs (and responsibility) of deployment. Multiple countries could develop the technology and gain negotiating power over the injection strategy. Coalitional outcomes are therefore possible, even if likely to be confined to a handful of powerful actors ¹⁵. However, our results show a robust pattern of vulnerability for sub-Saharan Africa, Southeast Asia, and Central American countries whenever we relax the hypothesis of full international cooperation. These countries don't have and might not develop the economic size, diplomatic weight or technological capacity to meaningfully influence the outcomes of coalitional deployments of SAI, suggesting they could remain losers of a larger set of SAI strategies.

Conclusions

This paper provides several methodological and policy-relevant contributions. We showcased how a climate emulator of the physical characteristics of SAI can be coupled with a high-resolution climate-economy model to explore the consequences of both idealized and sub-optimal geoengineering governance. This framework allows us to better explore the possibility space of geoengineering deployments, gaining insights into its spatial and social consequences. Of course, our results are dependent on our assumptions, and they should be interpreted only under these lenses. First, our analysis of physical and economic impacts of SAI is not exhaustive: if explicitly modelled, other SAI impacts like stratospheric ozone loss, acid sulphur deposition, and risk of termination shock ^{26,27} would contribute to the assessment with their own spatial footprint. Second, unilateral deployment of SAI would arguably, but not necessarily ¹⁰, hinder cooperation on emission reductions. If an underlying mitigation effort should survive the unilateral implementation of SAI, its physical and economic impact would be reduced. Furthermore, while it is unprecedented in its level of detail,

the country-level resolution of our model might still be insufficient for designing the strategy of sub-continentals like India or the US. Including sub-national climate variations could lead even unilateral deployers to choose more symmetric strategies, reducing their risks. Finally, the assumption of perfect information about climate states and preferences likely exaggerates the real-world capacity of tailoring a desirable SAI strategy, overestimating its benefits and downplaying the risks. Nonetheless, this paper provides a methodology for better capturing the regionally differentiated impacts of climate interventions and their consequences for the governance of solar geoengineering.

Methods

The climate-economy model

RICE50+ is an integrated assessment model featuring an iso3 resolution, calibrated marginal abatement cost curves and multiple impact functions³⁰. Regional temperature is linearly downscaled from global temperature increase using a linear emulator calibrated on the CMIP5 database. The model can produce both cost-effective (with pre-specified temperature, radiative forcing, or carbon budget targets), cost-benefit and hybrid scenarios. The model is suited to run a non-cooperative open loop Nash equilibrium, where each country/region solves independently its own welfare maximization problem until convergence of the global variable (i.e. global emission stock), but also a cooperative equilibrium, in which a global planner optimizes for a weighted and discounted sum of regional welfares. In this case, the utility function includes an inequality aversion term that attributes more (or less) weight to regions with low consumption per capita. Population and GDP projections are based on the SSP2 “middle-of-the-road” scenario. An open-source version of the model is available at <https://github.com/witch-team/RICE50xmodel>.

The model is advanced with three different features: regionalized SRM effectiveness, regionalized SRM side effects, and updating the climate-economic impact function. Regional temperature and precipitation are given by:

$$TEMP_{n,t} = \alpha_{n,T} + \beta_{n,T} * T_g + \sum_{z=-60}^{+60} \epsilon_{n,z,T} * SRM_{z,t}$$

$$PREC_{n,t} = (\alpha_{n,P} + \beta_{n,P} * T_g) * (1 + \sum_{z=-60}^{+60} \epsilon_{n,z,P} * SRM_{z,t})$$

Where α_n is the preindustrial local temperature (precipitation) of country n , β_n is the slope of the linear emulator for temperature (precipitation) as a function of global warming T_g due to carbon dioxide emissions (i.e. excluding SRM effects) which is

derived from the standard 3 layer model in RICE50+, and $\varepsilon_{n,z}$ is the cooling/precipitation variation given by a deployment at latitude z for country n . $\varepsilon_{n,z,T}$ is expressed in °C, while $\varepsilon_{n,z,P}$ is expressed the percentage variation from the baseline with climate change. The calibration of these parameters is described below in the section SAI emulator.

Zonal SRM deployment $SRM_{z,t}$ is given by the sum of injections by all countries at a certain latitude:

$$SRM_{z,t} = \sum_n SRM_{n,z,t}$$

Regional temperature and precipitation effect the per capita growth of the economy via the following quadratic equation:

$$IMPACT_{n,t,T} = a_{n,T} + b_{n,T} * TEMP_{n,t} + c_{n,T} * TEMP_{n,t}^2$$

$$IMPACT_{n,t,P} = a_{n,P} + b_{n,P} * PREC_{n,t} + c_{n,P} * PREC_{n,t}^2$$

The calibration of these coefficients is described in the section “climate emulator”. These impacts affect per capita economic growth with a persistence p_d , such that:

$$yd_{n,t} = yd_{n,t_0} * \prod_{t^*=1}^{t-p_d-1} (1 + g_{n,t^*})^{tstep} * \prod_{t^{**}=t-p_d}^t \left(1 + g_{n,t^{**}} + \sum_{d=T,P} IMPACT_{n,t^{**},d} \right)^{tstep}$$

With $g_{n,t}$ representing the baseline (exogenous) per capita growth that matches SSP projections for each country. Persistency is set to 10 years for temperature impacts and 5 years for precipitation impacts. Total damage fraction relative to gross output YG is then given by:

$$D_{n,t} = \frac{(YG_{n,t} - yd_{n,t} * pop_{n,t})}{YG_{n,t}}$$

Where $YG_{n,t}$ is baseline gross income and $pop_{n,t}$ is population.

These damages effect GDP with the same channel as in the main RICE50+ model, and costs of SAI are subtracted. Final output is given by:

$$Y_{n,t} = YG_{n,t} * (1 - D_{n,t}) - C_{SRM_{n,t}} - C_{ER_{n,t}}$$

Where $C_{ER_{n,t}}$ is the cost of emission reductions. The cost of SRM implementation is given for each country by:

$$C_{SRM_{n,t}} = \frac{c_{srm}}{\tau_{srm}} * \sum_z SRM_{n,z,t}$$

Consistently with Emmerling et al., the specific cost per TG of S injected c_{srm} is assumed to be 10 billion US \$/TgS and the residence time of Sulfur in the atmosphere τ_{srm} is assumed to be 2 years.

Temperature impact function

The coefficients $a, b, c_{n,T}$ are calibrated by modifying one empirically estimated damage function used in RICE50+35. In the original BHM formulation, each country prefers a local temperature of 12.5 °C. If taken literally, this implies that very hot countries (e.g. India, Sub Saharan African countries) would be willing to cool by more than 10°C. Vice versa, for cold countries, the preferred global warming exceeds 10°C Celsius. Clearly, no country would benefit from a new glacial era or from a level of warming that would collapse civilization. Therefore, we modify the impact function to maintain the ranking of temperature preference as it is in BHM formulation but shrink the range of preferred temperatures to 1°C between the “hottest” and “coldest” country. We impose for each country a quadratic form with the following conditions: We impose the maximum at the new, redefined, optimal temperature. At the average local temperature between 1990 and 2012 we assume damages to be zero, to respect the way the original impact function was constructed. we scale each regional impact curve such that, for a regional cooling of 2°C for countries with an optimal temperature lower than the baseline year temperature (e.g. hot countries) and for a regional warming of 2°C for countries with an optimal temperature higher than the baseline year temperature (e.g. cold countries), the old and the new formulation have the same impacts. In the original BHM function, the concavity of the curve is very low, approximating a linear function for credible ranges of temperature variations. To allow for a narrower range of local temperature optima, the new impact function introduces a visible concavity that underestimates the growth effects for low level of warming (cooling) and overestimates the growth effects high levels of warming (cooling), especially for equatorial and tropical countries. Nonetheless, the values are comparable for the range 2-3°C of warming.

Precipitation impact function

The calibration of the precipitation coefficients is based on ³⁶, which estimates the effect of annual mean precipitation, monthly variability, and extremes on economic growth with a sub-national historical panel. They find that mean precipitation increases economic output with diminishing marginal returns, but precipitation extremes and inter-annual variability hinder growth. Since variations in extremes and variability correlate with deviations in total annual precipitation the two effects

statistically counterbalance to produce negative growth effects for both a large increase and decrease in precipitations. The magnitude of the impacts is calibrated on ³⁶ damage function with the following procedure. First, we linearly relate the variation in annual mean precipitation $P_{t,n}$ with the variation in other relevant variables $X_{i,t,n}$ (extremes, monthly deviations, number of wet days) for each region relative to their historical mean:

$$\frac{X_{i,t,n} - \mu_n(X_i)}{\sigma_n(X_i)} = a_{i_n} \frac{P_{t,n} - \mu_n(P)}{\sigma_n(P)}$$

Standard deviations of historical mean are calculated from the regional precipitation and rainfall extremes distribution in 1979-2016, leveraging on the dataset used in Kotz et al. ^{1,30}, where GID1 (subnational) values for precipitation-based variables are available.

We use the estimate coefficients a_n to calculate for each country, the total economic effect predicted by the damage function for a given variation of annual mean precipitation from the historical mean, assuming the linear relations above hold exactly.

$$\Delta g_{n,N} = f(\mu_n(P), N * \sigma_n(P), a_{i_n}) - f_0(\mu_n(P), a_{i_n})$$

By evaluating this new function for different variations of annual mean precipitation ($N=\pm 1,2,3$) we can then produce country-level damage functions that depend only on annual mean precipitations. To assess the uncertainty introduced by this method, we consider the central estimates and the confidence interval of a_{i_n} . Results are shown in Extended Figure 6: dotted lines represent the median across countries of the estimated impact function for the central, low and high estimates of the correlation between extremes and annual mean precipitations. These specifications are roughly symmetrical for low correlations (except for high latitude countries) and foresee a preference for increased rainfall by tropical and equatorial countries for high correlations. Acknowledging this uncertainty, we use as a central specification one that conservatively considers the same negative marginal effect for a decrease and an increase in total annual precipitation.

The climate emulator

For the development of the emulator, we leverage data from ARISE-SAI simulations ³⁷. These simulations were conducted under the moderate Shared Socio-economic Pathway scenario of SSP2–4.5. We selected key variables, including reference height, mean temperature and total (convective and large scale) mean precipitation rate. These variables were simulated on a monthly basis from 2035 to 2069, utilizing a spatial grid with a resolution of 1.25° for longitude and 0.95° for latitude. In the ARISE-SAI simulations, sulphur dioxide injections were introduced at an altitude of

approximately 21.5 kilometres. These injections were positioned at seven distinct latitudes: 0°N, 15°S, 15°N, 30°S, 30°N, 60°S, and 60°N. This configuration led to seven sets of independent simulations. The injection rate was held constant at 12 Tg/year for each latitude, except at 60°N where 12 Tg was injected during March, April, and May, and at 60°S where injections occurred in September, October, and November. On average, the annual injected quantity remains consistent, allowing us to compare annual mean results. We consider an initial transition period and use simulations from 2050 to 2069, post-convergence of the controller³⁷. Population data is sourced from SEDAC projections (<https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/data/set/popdynamics-1-8th-pop-base-year-projection-ssp-2000-2100-rev01>). We extract the mean population value from 2030 to 2070. Population density in each grid cell is calculated by dividing the population value of each cell by the cell's area in square kilometres. In our analysis, we focus exclusively on land data. We compute the average temperature and precipitation differences over time for each injection strategy in the regions of interest, using an iso3 aggregation. We apply a weighting algorithm based on the population density of each grid cell, aligning the population density data with the gridded temperature and precipitation data. This approach provides us with mean temperature and precipitation differences values that are responsive to the most densely populated areas within each region.

We employ an aggregated model over time. Since the effects of injections are expected to be additive³⁸, we model the mean values over the 20 years of collected data after the stabilization of simulations. We leverage on two ensemble members simulations for each variable and estimate the model respectively on the separate members and on their mean values for testing results robustness. We fit a generalized additive fixed effect regression model, with automatic smoothness estimation based on penalized regression splines, to analyse average cooling in each region, namely the difference in temperature between the baseline with climate change and each injection simulation. This model incorporates the absolute distance of the region's centroid from the injection latitude (expressed as latitude degrees difference) and the injection latitude itself, interacting with region-specific effects, both fitted with smooth terms. A fixed effect accounting for different latitude bands is included, with bands defined as shown in Figure 1, to allow for externalities depending on the varying latitude of the samples to be accounted for. The model can be expressed as follows:

$$C_{r,i} = \alpha_{0r} + \alpha \cdot b_r + f_i(i, r) + f_d(d_r) + \varepsilon$$

With $C_{r,i}$ being the mean cooling over time with respect to baseline with climate change of region r for injection latitude i , α_{0r} characterizing the regions fixed effects, b_r indicating the bands fixed effects, $f_i(i, r)$ representing the smooth term for injection latitudes, differentiated in each region, and $f_d(d_r)$ the smooth term for distances of regions from injection points. Here, ε represents independent and identically distributed random errors with a normal distribution with zero mean. We estimate the

mean cooling for new values of injection latitudes (and consequently new values of distance from injection latitude), specifically assuming new injections at 45°S and 45°N.

A similar generalized additive fixed effect regression model is employed to analyse average precipitation difference between the baseline with climate change and each injection simulation, in each region. We deploy the same kind of model given its flexibility and to allow an easier comparison with the cooling model results. It again incorporates the absolute distance of the region's centroid from the injection latitude (expressed as latitude degrees difference) and the injection latitude itself, interacting with region-specific effects, both fitted with smooth terms. A fixed effect accounting for different latitude bands is included, with bands defined as before. This model can be expressed as follows:

$$D_{r,i} = \beta_{0r} + \beta \cdot b_r + g_i(i, r) + g_d(dr) + \varepsilon$$

With $D_{r,i}$ being the mean precipitation difference over time (in mm/day) with respect to baseline with climate change of region r for injection latitude i , β_{0r} characterizing the regions fixed effects, b_r indicating the band fixed effects, g_i representing the smooth term for injection latitudes, differentiated in each region, and g_d the smooth term for distances of regions from injection points. ε represents independent and identically distributed random errors with a normal distribution with zero mean. We again estimate the mean precipitation difference for new values of injection latitudes at 45°S and 45°N. Finally, we deploy the resulting cooling and precipitation differences resulting from 9 different injection latitudes in impact functions in RICE50+.

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4. Intertemporal funding of negative emissions in a multi-regional integrated assessment model

Introduction

Abiding the temperature target of the Paris agreement requires sharply reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the first half of the century and stabilizing carbon dioxide emissions at net-zero around 2050¹. The global carbon budget compatible with 1.5°C warming with respect to pre-industrial amounts to roughly one decade of current global carbon dioxide emissions. Decarbonizing the economy at the speed required to avoid a budget overshoot might still be possible in scenarios characterized

by quick and widespread shift to sustainable lifestyles and low final energy demand, but most pathways foresee a significant amount of net-negative emissions (190 GtCO₂ (0-310))². However, scenarios based on current policies and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) project a flat or slightly declining global CO₂ emissions profile in the next decade. The gap between the trajectory required to reach 1.5°C and the projection based on actual ambition could be significantly reduced, but not erased, if mid-century net-zero targets pledged by most major economies were achieved³. Even if countries were to abide to all their stated policies and pledges, the carbon budget for 1.5°C would be significantly overshoot before mid-century, and net-negative emissions amounting to 320 GtCO₂ (250-440 GtCO₂ considering NDCs until 2030) would be required in the second part of the century to replenish the exhausted budget².

Net-negative emissions deployed at such scale pose several challenges from a technological, environmental, and moral perspective⁴⁻⁷. Recently, it has been pointed out that such effort would also entail potentially prohibitive expenditure increase for the governments that must subsidize carbon dioxide removal (CDR) companies⁸. Similarly, negative emissions could entail significant inequality repercussion if the CDR industry was owned by private capital extracting rents from the carbon market⁹. To mitigate these effects and to establish responsibility for future CDR, some authors have advocated for the implementation of intertemporal mechanisms to finance net negative emissions¹⁰. Notably, Carbon Removal Obligations (CRO) have been proposed as a quasi-market policy instrument to oblige emitters to provide future carbon removal¹¹. The obligation would enter the balance sheet of the firm as a physical liability over which an interest rate must be paid, until an equivalent amount of carbon is removed from the atmosphere. From a macro-economic perspective, assuming no insolvency, perfect foresight, long-term planning horizon, and perfect information, this mechanism allows an exact match between the cost-opportunity of emitting in the present and the discounted cost of performing the removal. The interest rate applied to the carbon debt is a policy leverage that allows the policymaker to steer the market to produce the desired level of budget overshoot and, consequently, net-negative emissions. In principle, this interest rate can be differentiated across firms and countries to reflect heterogeneity in the reliability, institutional capacity, and societal preferences. Because the interest on carbon obligations is paid by the firms that generate the debt that are also responsible for the future removal, this system complies with the “polluter pays” principle and it avoids overburdening future generations with the cost of negative emissions.

The effectiveness and feasibility of intertemporal financing mechanisms such as the CROs depend on the policy instruments designed to incentivize CDR. Currently, the standard implicit assumption in integrated assessment modelling scenarios as well as in the specific policy literature¹² is that CDR should be integrated into the

abatement carbon market, which means that emitters and removal companies would face the same carbon price. This setting is the theoretical first best solution because it grants the optimal ratio between abatement and removal. However, depending on the relative shape of the removal and abatement cost curves and on the existence of de-facto constraints on the deployment of CDR, this market setting is the root of the budget and distributional problems cited above. In this direction, a case has been made¹³ to separate targets – and therefore markets – for abatement and negative emissions. Separating targets for carbon removal poses, in the real world, a whole series of economic and political-economy challenges. In a perfect information and perfect foresight setting, however, changing the prices of the markets would not change the optimal mitigation pathway given the boundaries conditions of the problem, unless within-country distributional considerations are explicitly accounted for in the utility function of the optimization. Instead, if intertemporal mechanisms are considered, the optimal solution might change because different pricing structures for CDR change the size of the fund necessary to finance the same amount of negative emissions, therefore the optimal profile of investments and, as a consequence, the economy.

This report presents four methodological contributions: first, we implement a CRO setting in the RICE50+ model, a multi-regional top-down Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) based on Nordhaus' DICE. This allows us to explore the implication of this policy instrument considering heterogeneity of mitigation and removal potential across regions, as well as its interaction with the broader economy. Second, we model an explicit marginal removal cost curve to be able to price correctly carbon removal in multiple policy settings. Third, we model these policy settings, consider both market and non-market instruments to finance negative emissions. Finally, we model the possibility of trading carbon removal across regions, including intertemporal trading of CROs (see ANNEX A for motivation and model development). In this report, we describe the model advancements and demonstrate them in a stylized scenario setting.

Methods

The general structure of the base model is based on DICE and is documented by Gazzotti¹⁴. The model represents 57 independent regions over a time horizon spanning until 2300. For each country or for a series of coalitions (including the grand coalition), it solves a problem of maximization of discounted utility represented as consumption per capita. The model is suitable for cost benefit analysis because it includes several impact functions from climate change and can simulate various policy options such as a carbon tax, a carbon budget or a temperature/radiative forcing limit. When more than one coalition is required, an open-loop Nash equilibrium

is searched by iteratively solving each coalition as a separate problem in parallel until global variables (e.g. the climate) converge.

Here, we briefly describe the main equations of the model relevant for this discussion. Capital letters indicate variables, lowercase indicate parameters, subscript indicate set dependencies (t is a model period, n a country/region) and $f(\cdot)$ indicate that f is a function of variable(s).

The economy is represented as a single-good, single-agent economy and total gross output $Y0$ is derived from a Cobb-Douglas production function as:

$$Y0_{t,n} = tfp_{t,n} * K_{t,n}^\alpha * pop_{t,n}^{1-\alpha}$$

Where the total factor productivity tfp is calibrated to match different socio-economic projections (SSP) for total output $Y0$ given exogenous population pop and assuming an optimal evolution of capital stock K . The dynamic of the capital stock K is given by:

$$K_{t+1,n} = K_{t,n} * (1 - \delta) + I_{t,n}$$

Where $\delta = 0.1$ is the exogenous depreciation rate of capital and investments I are defined as:

$$I_{t,n} = Y_{t,n} * S_{t,n}$$

With saving rates S being one of the two decision variables of the problem and final output Y is given by:

$$Y_{t,n} = Y0_{t,n} - Ca_{t,n}$$

Abatement costs Ca are defined by:

$$Ca_{t,n} = \int_0^{A_{t,n}} mac_{t,n}(A_{t,n}) * ebase_{t,n} * dA$$

With A defined as the fraction of baseline emission $ebase$ abated, and $mac(A)$ representing the marginal abatement cost curve described as a polynomial of order 4 (with coefficient of the first and the fourth order):

$$mac_{t,n}(A_{t,n}) = P_{t,n}^4(A_{t,n})$$

The coefficients of the polynomial are calibrated using marginal abatement cost curves based on the POLES model and data from the IPCC SR15 database, and they are country-dependent to reflect heterogeneity in the mitigation profiles as well as time-dependent to represent (exogenous) technical learning.

Consumption C is given by the final output minus investments:

$$C_{t,n} = Y_{t,n} - I_{t,n}$$

The optimization problem maximizes over the free variables A and S the sum of consumption per capita across time and regions within the coalition discounted for intertemporal elasticity of substitution η and for inequality aversion ρ :

$$\sum_{t,n} f\left(\frac{C_{t,n}}{pop_{t,n}}, \eta, \rho\right)$$

In our cost-effective setting, the optimization problem is constrained by the following condition on cumulative CO₂ emissions:

$$\sum_{t=t_0}^{t_{end}} E_{t,n} < cbudget_n \quad t_{end} \geq 2100$$

Where $cbudget$ represents the regional carbon budget accruing to each region n and emissions E are defined by:

$$E_{t,n} = EPOS_{t,n} = ci_{t,n} * Y_{t,n} * (1 - A_{t,n})$$

With the carbon intensity of GDP ci is calibrated to match baseline emissions and GDP from different socio-economic projections from the IPCC SR15 scenario database, $ebase_{t,n} = ci_{t,n} * Y_{t,n}$.

Separated negative emissions

In the standard DICE model, CDR and conventional emission reductions are aggregated into the same cost curve. If the abatement control variable A exceeds 100% net-negative emissions are reached. However, in such a setting it is impossible to distinguish between gross abatement and gross removals, hence the total CDR amount is not clearly specified. The need to quantify the amount and price of CDR requires a disaggregation of the cost curve into separate curves for conventional abatement (emission reductions) and CDR.

In addition to the conventional abatement fraction A , we define CDR related abatement as the removal ratio $R = \frac{ENEG}{ebase}$, adding $ENEG$ as a new decision variable in the optimization. Total emissions are now given by:

$$E_{t,n} = EPOS_{t,n} - ENEG_{t,n}$$

And the removal cost is described by the following marginal removal cost curve (MRCC):

$$mrc_{t,n}(R_{t,n}) = f0_t * (1 - e^{\tau * R_{t,n}}) + f1 * R_{t,n}^{f2}$$

From which total removal cost Cr follows:

$$Cr_{t,n} = \int_0^{ENEG_{t,n}} mrc_{t,n} \left(\frac{ENEG_{t,n}}{ebase_{t,n}} \right) dENEG$$

And enters the income equation as:

$$Y_{t,n} = Y0_{t,n} - Ca_{t,n} - Cr_{t,n}$$

The term $f0_t$ represents the baseline cost of our representative negative emission technology. The baseline cost exogenously decreases with time, simulating technological development on currently immature technologies. The cost is based on projections for DACS technology, starting from a cost of removal of 453 \$/tonCO₂ in the year 2020 and reaching a floor cost of 100 \$/tonCO₂ from the year 2070 onwards. Simulating experience curves, the baseline cost approaches exponentially the floor cost, and the learning rate can be set to different values to simulate different cost profiles evolutions for the technologies. The term $(1 - e^{-\tau * R_{t,n}})$ bridges the floor cost of removal to zero for computational stability reasons, with τ being a large number. Permanence of removal is assumed. The second term $f1 * R_{t,n}^{f2}$ represents a standard power law used for abatement cost curves that provides a convex shape to the abatement curve and simulates factors such as land competition for BECCS or increased energy requirement for DACS. We assume a quadratic shape for the removal curve, i.e. $f2 = 2$, meaning that the increase in costs for removal is in general smoother than for abatement (an order 4 polynomial).

Varying how the parameter $f1$ is constructed, we model several possible different characterizations of the marginal removal curve summarized in Table 1:

1. Flat marginal cost curve, i.e. the CDR acts like a backstop technology. If carbon removal is assumed unbounded, this setting produces a perfect backstop technology with a price $f0_t$. Regional constraints Rup_n can be allocated according to several possible rules described below, in which case CDR assumes the characteristics of a bounded backstop technology, i.e. with an average cost $f0_t$ before the constraint and infinite afterwards.
2. A condition that grants that, for a set of regional constraints on the removal capacity, the marginal cost of removal at the point in the curve corresponding to the constraint equals the marginal cost of fully abating emissions. The hard constraint on the variable is then removed, to avoid truncations in the pricing profile under particular market conditions (for example, in case of net-negative emissions).
3. A condition that grants that removal is regionally cheaper than abatement after 75% of regional emissions are abated. We set this condition for 2100, i.e. assuming full technological maturity of both standard abatement options and CDR options. This condition follows Belaia and colleagues' assumption¹⁵. In a regional setting, assuming this cost profile changes the costs of mitigating

climate change within each region, but in a global cost-effective mitigation profile it does not change the share of total mitigation effort accruing to each region in the period the constraint is set for. Because both profile costs evolve with different speeds, however, this is not true before 2100.

Table 1: Characterizations of the marginal removal curve

	Shape	Derivation
Backstop technology	Flat	$f1 = 0$
Regional constraints	Quadratic	$f1_{t,n} = mac_{t,n}(1) - \frac{f0_t}{R, up_n f^2}$
McKingsley	Quadratic	$f1_n = ebase_{2100,n} * mac_{2100,n}(0.75) - \frac{f0_{2100}}{0.75f^2}$

Regional constraints R, up_n can be set to limit the maximum removal allowed in each region. This constraint, given a maximum global amount of CDR allowed per year $ENEG, up$, can be allocated with various formulas summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Allocation of CDR

	Allocation	Formula
Geological constraint	According to total storage capacity $stor_n$ for each region.	$R, up_n = \frac{ENEG, up}{ebase_{t,n}} * \frac{stor_n}{\sum_n stor_n}$
DACS	According to ISO3 level potential for DACS from dac_n .	$R, up_n = \frac{ENEG, up}{ebase_{t,n}} * dac_n$
BECCS	According to ISO3 level potential for BECCS from $beccs_n$.	$R, up_n = \frac{ENEG, up}{ebase_{t,n}} * beccs_n$
Equal per capita	More populous regions perform more removal.	$R, up_n = \frac{ENEG, up}{ebase_{t,n}} * \frac{\sum_{t=2020}^{2100} pop_{t,n}}{\sum_{t=2020,n}^{2100} pop_{t,n}}$

Historical responsibility	More historically responsible regions perform more removal.	$R, up_n = \frac{ENEG, up}{ebase_{t,n}} * \frac{\sum_{t=1900}^{2020} E_{t,n}}{\sum_{t=1900,n}^{2020} E_{t,n}}$
Grandfathering	Current emitters perform more removal.	$R, up_n = \frac{ENEG, up}{ebase_{t,n}} * \frac{E_{2015,n}}{\sum_n E_{2015,n}}$
Unbounded	No hard constraint is set.	$R, up_n = +\infty$

Finally, geological storage is subjected to a physical constraint on the regional cumulative capacity of the removal, such that cumulative carbon stored in geological formations cannot exceed regional storage capacity $stor_n$. Costs of storage are not explicitly considered in this setting.

This representation of CDR costs and potential is highly stylized, because of the lack of reliable country-level data on cost curve of removal for CDR. However, this structure reflects many qualitative characteristics of the carbon removal market and is sufficiently flexible to be calibrated to a wide variety of technologies (or technology mixes) of negative emission technologies.

The intertemporal fund

The CRO framework is modelled as a regional fund that is filled through revenues created by charging a price on carbon debt. Carbon debt D is defined as industrial emissions exceeding some temporal distribution of the carbon budget $e, up_{t,n}$ (e.g. a cap-and-trade system compatible with the total carbon budget assigned):

$$D_{t,n} = E_{t,n} - e, up_{t,n}$$

The fund is later depleted by expenditures required for gross removals, which in total equal carbon debt. The fund represents the aggregate fraction of total assets that perfectly solvent firms must allocate to be able to pay for future removal. Alternatively, the fund can be interpreted as a sovereign fund in which firms are obliged to pay in when they exceed the allowances in the cap-and-trade system. Like pension funds, this fund would be handled by governments and invested in capital assets to grow at the marginal productivity of capital rate and be discharged to pay the carbon removal. In a single-agent, single-good economy with perfect foresight, no strategic interaction among actors within society, and no risk premia, the two representations are functionally equal.

Capital accumulated in the fund F contributes to total production in the Cobb-Douglas production function and the gross income equation is modified accordingly:

$$Y_{0,t,n} = t f p_{t,n} * (K_{t,n} + F_{t,n})^\alpha * p o p_{t,n}^{1-\alpha}$$

To grant that the marginal productivity of investing into the fund equals final goods capital K , the fund is modelled as a depreciable stock with the same rate of depreciation of capital δ of final goods capital:

$$F_{t+1,n} = F_{t,n} * (1 - \delta) + I_{t,n} * F F_{t,n} + I F_{t,n} - D I F_{t,n}$$

The investments into the fund $I F$ depend on the carbon debt generated and on the price of the abatement carbon market $P A$:

$$I F_{t,n} = D_{t,n} * P a_{t,n}$$

This condition arises because, at the equilibrium, firms must be indifferent whether to obtain an allowance to emit, abate emissions or generate carbon debt and pay into the fund. Therefore, these three prices (price of the carbon market, marginal abatement cost, unit cost of generating carbon debt) must coincide.

Disinvestments from the fund $D I F$ equal the carbon removal at the price of the removal carbon market $P r$:

$$D I F_{t,n} = E N E G_{t,n} * P r_{t,n}$$

Finally, the term $I_{t,n} * F F_{t,n}$, with the fraction of fund over total productive capital $F F$ defined as:

$$F F_{t,n} = \frac{F_{t,n}}{F_{t,n} + K_{t,n}}$$

It grants that a part of the standard investment channel I is invested into the fund to compensate for the depreciation of capital. This condition grants that, at a certain time t and with an initial capital stock $K \neq 0$ and fund stock $F \neq 0$, if no other injection or removal from the fund is performed the ratio $F F$ remains constant in the next time step, i.e. that the fund grows at the same rate as capital K if no carbon debt is generated or withdrawal is performed.

When carbon debt is generated, investments into the fund are subtracted from consumption:

$$C_{t,n} = Y_{t,n} * (1 - S_{t,n}) - I F_{t,n}$$

Similarly, when the removal is paid for at the average or marginal cost of removal, resources are subtracted from the fund and introduced back in the economy:

$$Y_{t,n} = Y0_{t,n} - Ca_{t,n} - Cr_{t,n} + DIF_{t,n}$$

Finally, the fund must be greater or equal than zero at each point in time:

$$F_{t,n} \geq 0 \quad \forall t$$

The fund can be penalized assuming an interest rate IR , implemented through an additive term in the income equation written as:

$$-(F_{t,n,iter} - F_{t,n,iter-1}) * IR$$

Where $iter$ and $iter - 1$ identify the current and previous iterations of the solution algorithm. This grants that, at convergence, the interest rate is not lost in the economy (because it assumed to be recycled back into it) while still introducing a penalty proportional to the chosen interest rate and the amount of the fund.

Market options

We have introduced the prices for emission abatement $Pa_{t,n}$ and for carbon removal $Pr_{t,n}$. In most scenario applications of integrated assessment models, these two prices are assumed to coincide and are prescribed by some exogenous growth rate rule, usually Hotelling. This is equivalent to assuming the integration of CDR technologies into the abatement carbon market. However, a single market can create a variety of conceptual and practical problems. Here, we explicitly model various alternative market configurations for the regulation of prices and quantities in the CDR market. Each of these options can be considered with or without the intertemporal financing mechanisms described above.

The standard policy setting considered is a single carbon market. This is given by the condition:

$$Pa_{t,n} = Pr_{t,n} = (mrc_{t,n}(R_{t,n}), mac_{t,n}(A_{t,n}))$$

i.e. the price of the market is given by the most expensive ton of carbon abated or removed at the margin.

In addition, we consider a setting in which the price of the market is uniform but defined only by the marginal abatement cost curve:

$$Pa_{t,n} = Pr_{t,n} = mac_{t,n}(A_{t,n})$$

This corresponds to a market designed for mitigation in which CDR is integrated. To grant at least a zero-profit condition for CDR companies, if the price of the market is lower than the average cost of removal, subsidies $S_{t,n}$ (expressed per ton of carbon removed) can be assigned to CDR companies, such that:

$$S_{t,n} = \max \left(\frac{Cr_{t,n}}{ENEG_{t,n}} - Pr_{t,n}, 0 \right)$$

Secondly, we consider a policy setting with two separate prices and markets for CDR and abatement. In this case, the carbon price for each market is given, for abatement, by:

$$Pa_{t,n} = mac_{t,n}(A_{t,n})$$

For removal, we allow for two different settings: the first one that simulated a separate carbon market or a carbon tax in which the price is given by the marginal unit of CDR dispatched, and a second one in which the price equals the average cost of removal. This second setting simulates a non-market structure in which a certain amount of CDR is deployed by state or public entities or a market in which a zero-profit condition is forced over the CDR companies, assuming no strategic behaviour, no asymmetry of information and no cost of information for the regulator of the market. These two conditions are given by:

$$Pr_{t,n} = mrc_{t,n}(R_{t,n}) \quad \text{OR} \quad Pr_{t,n} = \frac{Cr_{t,n}}{ENEG_{t,n}}$$

Demonstrative results

Scenarios

We compare modelling results for a 1150 GtCO₂ carbon budget compatible with 2 °C at 50% probability according to AR6 WGI reached with and without the availability of negative emissions (Figure 1). We allow for a temporary overshoot of the total budget before the end of the century, i.e. regional and global emissions can become net-negative. All scenarios follow a historical responsibility distribution of the total carbon budget. Negative emissions, when active, are characterized following the McKingsley assumption. This assumption implies that the availability of negative emissions changes the intertemporal cost profile but not the international distribution of it, given that it constructs the regional marginal removal cost curves with a fixed rule that links them to each regional abatement cost curve. This is a useful assumption to test the model's capacities but does not reflect the reality that mitigation and removal potential are distributed unequally across regions. We run the model in the R5 regional configuration.

Separated negative emissions

To test the effect of the newly introduced negative emission technology in RICE50+, we compare two scenarios with and without the availability of negative emissions (Figure 1). Please note that the scenario without negative emissions assumes no possibility of offsetting whatsoever. Therefore, it must not be interpreted as a scenario

that does not allow net-negative emissions, but one in which no negative emissions technologies are available. Introducing negative emissions allows for budget overshoot and greatly diminishes the total mitigation costs and consumption losses for most of the century (Figure 1c). Roughly one third of the total budget available is removed from the atmosphere with negative emissions (Figure 1a). The regional share of budget and costs is not significantly affected by the introduction of negative emissions (Figure 1d and Figure 1b) because of the McKingsley assumption. Because the optimal solution equalizes mitigation options at the margin (Figure 1e), the marginal removal and abatement cost curves are equal and closely resemble a Hotelling profile. Average costs are higher for removal because we assume a quadratic shape for removal and a quartic for abatement.

Figure 1: (a) Global emissions divided by source (sink). Bars represent the cumulative between 2020-2100 for each type. Dotted black lines compare the net emissions of the other scenario. (b1) regional mapping (b2) regional distribution of the carbon budget across regions (b3) difference between scenario 1 and 2 in carbon removed and abated cumulatively between 2020 and 2100 across regions. (c) global costs divided by source. "Growth effects" represents the variation in the saving rates and include the effects of the intertemporal fund, if present. Black lines represent net GDP losses and red lines net consumption losses, as % of the baseline (climate damage is not taken into account). (d) share of costs across regions over time. (e) marginal and average prices (global median) for removal and abatement across scenarios. (f) variation of investments and capital stocks as % of baseline GDP between scenario 1 and scenario 2. Black dashed line represents net variation. (g) total value of the fund and distribution across regions.

Fund Introduction

We now compare two scenarios with and without the introduction of the intertemporal fund (Figure 2) in which carbon removal is priced at its average cost. This is equivalent to forcing a zero-profit condition to the removal companies, that therefore don't participate in the carbon market. As expected, the two scenarios produce the exact same result (net of numerical variability) in terms of the overall emissions profile, the distribution of abatement and removal, and consumption losses, as well as the net capital and investments profile. The scenarios only differ in GDP losses, because the fund is partly discharged in the second part of the century to pay for net-negative emissions that increase GDP (see Figure 2e, grey area). However, the increase in GDP and consequent decrease of the capital stock related to the fund is exactly compensated by an increase in investments in final goods, such that the overall capital stock and investment profiles (black lines in Figure 2f) do not change across the two scenarios. Interestingly, because the fund is completely interchangeable with capital and not penalized with an interest rate on carbon debt in this scenario, it is not exhausted in 2100. This happens for two reasons.

First, because the market for offsetting and the market for repayment of the carbon debt are assumed to be priced equally, i.e. all negative emissions are repaid at the same price regardless that they are used for intra-temporal or inter-temporal offsetting of carbon debt. Because at the equilibrium the marginal price of abatement and removal equalize, average costs of removal are significantly lower than the marginal cost of abatement that defines the price for the abatement market (dark orange line vs light blue line in Figure 2e). From a financial perspective, it means that offsetting intra-temporally one unit of emissions with removal implies an investment in the fund as we defined it. Therefore, a policy setting with average pricing for removal and marginal pricing for abatement generates an "extra-saving" in the fund

than what's needed to pay for the repayment of the carbon debt after net-zero emissions.

Second, because the fund is filled in by carbon debt paid at the carbon price for abatement, i.e. marginal abatement cost. However, the quantities linked through the discount rate are the average and not the marginal costs, in the sense that the social planner equalizes the discounted average cost of removing a ton of carbon in the future and in the present.

Figure 2: (a) Global emissions divided by source (sink). Bars represent the cumulative between 2020 and net-zero year and 2020-2100 for each type of source-sink. Dotted black lines compare the net emissions of the other scenario. (b1) regional mapping (b2) regional distribution of the carbon budget across regions (b2) difference between scenario 1 and 2 in carbon removed and abated cumulatively between 2020 and 2100

across regions. (c) global costs divided by source. “Growth effects” represents the variation in the saving rates and include the effects of the intertemporal fund, if present. Black lines represent net GDP losses and red lines net consumption losses, as % of the baseline. (d) share of costs across regions over time. (e) marginal and average prices (global median) for removal and abatement across scenarios. (f) variation of investments and capital stocks as % of baseline GDP between scenario 1 and scenario 2. Black dotted line represents net variation. (g) total value of the fund and distribution across regions.

The latter condition derives from the fact that, at equilibrium, an emitter must be indifferent to abate, pay the carbon price for abatement, or invest into the fund for future removal, and is therefore forced. The former condition, however, is a policy choice, in the sense that one could in principle design a single market for intra-temporal offsetting, where the price is given by the maximum of the marginal abatement and marginal removal cost curves (i.e. by the most expensive unit of carbon avoided), and a separate financial mechanisms for intertemporal carbon debt in which only the fraction of carbon removal associated with replenishment of the carbon budget is accounted for and priced at the average cost. In our setting, defining ND as the net carbon debt generated by region n at time t and NC the net carbon credit (i.e. the net-negative fraction of carbon removal):

$$ND_{t,n} = \max (E_{t,n} - R_{t,n} - e, up_{t,n}, 0)$$

$$NC_{t,n} = -\min (E_{t,n} - R_{t,n} - e, up_{t,n}, 0)$$

The fund would then be invested in and disinvested from according to the following equations:

$$IF_{t,n} = ND_{t,n} * Pa_{t,n}$$

$$DIF_{t,n} = NC_{t,n} * Pr_{t,n}$$

Figure 3 compares such a setting with the previous one. Indeed, the optimal solution (in terms of emissions) does not change but the amount saved into the fund is significantly reduced (10% of baseline GDP) and the fund follows a bell shape through the century, depleting towards 2100. It should be noted that this policy structure has the merit of producing a better time profile for the fund, i.e. one in which the fund is completely depleted after budget overshoot. However, it creates a conceptual and policy problem, because it separates the market for offsets and for the carbon budget replenishment. This means that, after net-zero, a carbon removal company could access two markets: one competitive, priced at the marginal cost of the most expensive unit deployed or ton of carbon abated; the other one regulated, where each company is compensated for their total cost of removal. Because firms would naturally decide to enter the competitive market if they assume they can extract a

profit for the market, this would leave the overshoot replenishment market to the most expensive firms/technologies, i.e. the ones for which the average cost of removal equals the marginal cost of the market. A scenario in which the “average quality” firm is tasked with carbon debt replenishment can arise only if removal is either performed by a public institution or secured via long-term contracts between the entities that generate the net carbon debt and the carbon removal companies, that would allow to fix the price.

Figure 3: (a) Global emissions divided by source (sink). Bars represent the cumulative between 2020 and net-zero year and 2020-2100 for each type of source-sink. Dotted black lines compare the net emissions of the other scenario. (b1) regional mapping (b2) regional distribution of the carbon budget across regions (b2) difference between scenario 1 and 2 in carbon removed and abated cumulatively between 2020 and 2100 across regions. (c) global costs divided by source. “Growth effects” represents the

variation in the saving rates and include the effects of the intertemporal fund, if present. Black lines represent net GDP losses and red lines net consumption losses, as % of the baseline. (d) share of costs across regions over time. (e) marginal and average prices (global median) for removal and abatement across scenarios. (f) variation of investments and capital stocks as % of baseline GDP between scenario 1 and scenario 2. Black dotted line represents net variation. (g) total value of the fund and distribution across regions.

Marginal pricing with intertemporal fund

Introducing the intertemporal fund when negative emissions are priced at their average costs (i.e. a zero-profit condition is forced upon each removal option) produces a “neutral” solution in the sense that it doesn’t change the optimal mitigation profile. With the same budget and settings, we now explore the effects of pricing negative emissions at their marginal costs. This simulates the creation of a separate market for removal, in which the price can be different from the abatement market. Figure 4 compares the previously discussed average pricing setting with the marginal pricing setting with double markets for abatement and removal. Because it regulates the amount of disinvestments in the fund, marginal pricing has an effect on the optimal pathway, affecting both the mitigation profile, the costs and consumption loss profile, and the optimal investment rate. De facto, pricing negative emissions at the marginal removal costs imply that in the fund is saved not only an amount of resources necessary to cover for the future costs of overshoot, but also to pay the profit margin to the carbon removal companies in the future carbon market (defined as revenues minus cost). In this sense, pricing at the margin with an intertemporal fund effectively generates a transfer of wealth between present and future generation, visible in the greater GDP increase in the second part of the century relative to the average pricing scenario due to the discharging of the fund at the marginal price (Figure 4c). This trend is reflected, while less marked, also in the consumption loss pattern that is higher before net-zero and lower thereafter relative to the average pricing scenario. Because the model is, due to the discount rate, adverse to transferring wealth from the present to the future, marginal pricing of CDR also influences the amount of negative and net-negative emissions deployed in the century to reach the carbon budget: in particular, negative emissions are reduced both before net-zero emissions (i.e. less offsetting) and after net-zero (i.e. less overshoot). However, it should be noted that, despite the significant difference in the pricing profile for negative emissions (more than 2x), the difference in negative emissions deployed is moderate (50 GtCO₂ less removed through the century, 20% of total removal). Consequently, the marginal costs of abatement and removal (that reflect the corresponding carbon prices) diverge, with a lower carbon price for the removal market. Finally, the temporal trajectory (as well as the sheer size) of the intertemporal fund changes: because of higher mitigation in the first part of the century, where

abatement happens in the relatively flat region of the marginal abatement cost curve (i.e. where a large increase in mitigated emissions – i.e. reduction of carbon debt - causes a relatively low increase in the marginal abatement cost), the investments in the fund are reduced. Moreover, at the beginning of the century, the marginal price of removal and abatement are roughly equal which implies that the physical equality of abatement and removal is reflected in the financial structure of the fund, i.e. intra-temporal offsetting doesn't cause – as with average cost pricing for negative emissions – a net injection in the fund.

Figure 4: (a) Global emissions divided by source (sink). Bars represent the cumulative between 2020-2100 for each type. Dotted black lines compare the net emissions of the other scenario. (b1) regional mapping (b2) regional distribution of the carbon budget across regions (b2) difference between scenario 1 and 2 in carbon removed and abated cumulatively between 2020 and 2100 across regions. (c) global costs

divided by source. "Growth effects" represents the variation in the saving rates and include the effects of the intertemporal fund, if present. Black lines represent net GDP losses and red lines net consumption losses, as % of the baseline. (d) share of costs across regions over time. (e) marginal and average prices (global median) for removal and abatement across scenarios. (f) variation of investments and capital stocks as % of baseline GDP between scenario 1 and scenario 2. Black dotted line represents net variation. (g) total value of the fund and distribution across regions.

In the second part of the century, furthermore, the fund is discharged approximately twice as fast because negative emissions companies are paid for at the marginal cost of removal. The combined effect of these factors gives the fund profile a bell shape that peaks closer to the end of the modelling period (compare panels (f) of Figures 3 and 4).

Because of the pricing structure, this scenario setting resolves the aforementioned tension between a market for offsetting and for carbon debt replenishment: net debt generated in the first part of the century will be replenished, after net-zero, issuing a request for negative emissions at the carbon market for removal. In this sense, no functional difference exists in this setting between intra- and inter- temporal offsetting.

Conclusions

We showed that, when designing intertemporal policy instruments, the market or non-market structure of the policy instruments designed to pay for negative emissions' provision matters significantly. In particular, we find that a market structure characterized by separate prices for removal and abatement that coincide with the respective marginal costs influences the optimal solution of a carbon budget scenario both in terms of optimal emission profile (reducing negative emissions) and of policy costs profile (increasing consumption and GDP losses in the first part of the century and reducing them in the second), assuming that the generation of carbon debt is linked to carbon removal via a financial constraint that forces to invest a sufficient amount of resources to pay for negative emissions. This happens because marginal pricing for carbon removal (assuming a non-flat marginal removal cost curve) implies a shift of wealth between the present and the future, because present emitters must save to pay not only for the cost of future removal but also for the profits of future CDR companies. Because the social planner is averse to such transfer, it reduces the amount of net-negative emissions in the second half of the century. This is a relevant consideration, because the discussion about intertemporal instruments to finance net-negative emissions fundamentally arises from intergenerational equity consideration. However, the implications of transferring a rent for negative emissions have been, so far, overlooked. Furthermore, this rent shift has ethical consequences not only from an

intergenerational perspective but relates also to the income distribution: if companies providing for negative emissions are privately owned, their profits will benefit those who own capital and wealth, that are disproportionately located at the top of the income distribution. We argue that the combined inter-generational and within country distributional effects of such instruments should be carefully assessed to ensure that an intertemporal mechanism to finance large-scale net-negative emissions doesn't come with detrimental consequences in terms of equity and justice.

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ANNEX A: Work in progress on modelling advancements, trading carbon removal obligations

Motivation for trading negative emissions and intertemporal permits CDR affects not only intergenerational but also international equity, because it can be used as a burden-sharing tool^{16,17}. In most IPCC scenarios, regional shares of the remaining global carbon budget are implicitly derived by the application of a global uniform carbon tax growing exponentially at the market interest rate according to the Hotelling rule. This is the most efficient allocation possible (intertemporally and internationally, as well as across sectors) for a depletable resource if no path-dependencies are

considered ¹⁸. However, a cost-efficient solution implies large emission reductions in developing regions, that face a high mitigation burden with little historical emission responsibility. The “common but differentiated responsibilities” principle stated in the Paris agreement suggests that either large international transfers or alternative effort-sharing formulas must be explored to find solutions that integrate historical responsibilities and the heterogeneous capacity for facing the costs of the energy transition. In this context, it has been argued that CDR can be used as a progressive instrument ¹⁷ to redistribute the global mitigation effort, because it allows countries with a large historical carbon footprint to comply with a reduced or even negative carbon budget at the benefit of developing nations.

The equity-efficiency conundrum that arises from carbon budget allocation can be mitigated by allowing the trading of emission permits. Under the assumption of perfect markets, foresight, and information, for a social-planner maximizing equal-per-capita discounted consumption, and with full banking and borrowing of permits, the optimal profile of emission abatement does not change if the initial carbon budget allocation is changed. However, different initial budget allocations shape the magnitude and direction of traded permits and financial transfers. Therefore, under a global frictionless carbon market for emissions, assigning regional carbon budgets can be functionally traced back to a (properly designed) system of financial transfers. In other words, if trading is not allowed, assigning regional carbon budgets has first order (i.e. cost efficiency) and second-order (i.e. distributional) consequences. Under trading, different effort sharing formulas entail only distributional effects. In principle, this property can be exploited to design a global mitigation scenario that is both efficient and equitable.

In practice, several challenges arise because transaction and monitoring costs for trading emission reductions are non-negligible, and international trading of emissions requires trust between the state-actors involved, given the uncertainty that the other party will fulfil the obligation against the incentive to sell allowances and cheat on emission reductions. For these reasons international trading of emission permits has seen limited application in the real world, with the notable exception of the EU emission trading scheme. In this sense CDR, if intended as atmospheric removal and geological storage of carbon (with technologies such as Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage – BECCS, or Direct Air Capture and Storage - DACS), might provide an opportunity because physical flows of carbon stored can be monitored and verified at relatively low cost by independent third-party bodies, similarly to nuclear inspection. On the other hand, trading only negative emissions introduces limits the efficiency of the solution, both because it restricts tradable emission permits to a fraction of the mitigation potential of each country and because CDR potential is limited regionally, which further bounds the optimal solution. Nevertheless, trading exclusively negative emissions could be seen as more feasible and acceptable than a

full integration of carbon markets, and it is therefore a policy setting worth exploring on its own. While a rich theoretical and empirical literature exists about emission trading, no attempt exists so far to quantify the physical and financial implications of trading negative emissions, given their characteristics of costs and potential heterogeneity.

In this context, we aim to explore the connection between international instruments to financing of negative emissions (i.e. trading) and intertemporal instruments to finance negative emissions (i.e. CROs). We extend the concept of Carbon Removal Obligations into Tradable Carbon Removal Obligations (TCRO). These tradable permits would allow to track the emission-removal responsibility chain, both from a moral and economic standpoint, not only across generations but also across national borders. Under the availability of this policy instrument, we want to explore the conditions of costs and potential of CDR under which TCRO can be effectively used to improve the equity of the climate transition.

Trading carbon removal obligations

Given the heterogeneity of removal costs implied by the structure of the marginal removal cost curves, the opportunity of trading negative emissions arises because it equalizes the cost removal at the margin, i.e. it allows to fully exploit the potential of negative emission technologies across regions. Moreover, it allows regions to exceed their regional carbon budget over the century, the fact of outsourcing part of it to other regions.

Trading negative emissions requires three conditions. First, because we assume a perfect and frictionless global market, each regional carbon removal market price must coincide with the global market price of negative emissions Pm :

$$Pr_{t,n} = Pm_t$$

This condition has various implications with respect to the feasible policy and modelling setting described in the previous section. First, because we assume that trade is market driven, it is compatible only with a competitive carbon market for negative emissions, i.e. marginal pricing. Second, because we don't trade emissions permits for abatement, this setting is conceptually incompatible with a single carbon market because it would introduce distortions within each regional carbon market. Finally, trading is computationally incompatible with hard constraints on CDR maximum removal potential. Therefore, only representation (2) of the MRC described above can be used with trading.

The second is a market clearing condition and ensures that traded negative emissions (defined positive as imports of carbon removal) sum to zero for each time step:

$$\sum_n Em_{t,n} = 0$$

Third, we ensure that each region trades at most the carbon it physically removes:

$$ENEG_{t,n} > Em_{t,n}$$

Finally, exported permits for negative emissions is subtracted from the regional carbon budget constraint, because exporting CROs permits allow to outsource the carbon removal and increase the available budget. Vice versa, for an importer of permits, the part of physical carbon removal performed to fulfill foreign carbon removal obligations does not benefit the regional carbon budget and is therefore subtracted:

$$\sum E_{t,n} - Em_{t,n} < cbudget_n$$

Emissions trading can be combined with the intertemporal fund modifying the disinvestment profile from the fund as follows:

$$DIF_{t,n} = (ENEG_{t,n} - Em_{t,n}) * Pm_t$$

The quantity $ENEG_{t,n} - Em_{t,n}$ represents the virtual removal associate to each region, i.e. the amount of carbon removal physically deployed domestically $ENEG_{t,n}$ plus the amount of carbon removal outsourced abroad $-Em_{t,n}$.

Therefore, an exporter of carbon removal obligations permits will divest from the fund an additional quantity $-Em_{t,n}) * Pm_t$ that is needed to reward the importer of the CRO at the market carbon price. On the opposite, an importer of CROs will subtract from the fund only the fraction $ENEG_{t,n} - Em_{t,n}$ of the total physical removal $ENEG_{t,n}$, because $-Em_{t,n}$ is paid for by the exporter of TCRO.

In the income equation, only the physical removal (both for domestic reduction and for the carbon removal performed to fulfill imported TCROs) is reinjected into the economy, such that:

$$Y_{t,n} = Y0_{t,n} - Ca_{t,n} - Cr_{t,n} + ENEG_{t,n} * Pm_t$$